

5G META

D6.1

Market research and
stakeholder mapping

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
CCAM	Cooperative, Connected Automated Mobility
mMTC	Massive Machine Type Communications
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broadband
xMBB	Extreme Mobile Broadband
RSI	Roadside Infrastructure
OBU	On Board Unit
RSU	Roadside Unit
UC	Use Case
C-V2X	Cellular V2X
V2X	Vehicle-to-everything
V2I	Vehicle-to-Infrastructure
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
SME	Small Medium Enterprise
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
ADAS	Advanced Driver Assistance Systems
OEM	Original equipment manufacturer
5GAA	5G Automotive Association
3GPP	3 rd Generation Partnership Project
5G-PPP	5G Public Private Partnership
ACES	Autonomous driving, Connectivity, Electrification, and Shared mobility trends
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
SDN	Software Defined Networking
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
TSN	Time Sensitive Networking
SLA	Service Level Agreement

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

As part of the 5GMETA project, WP6 (New Market Ecosystem) has the objective to support the strategy to create a new CCAM (Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility) market ecosystem. In particular, Task 6.1 (Market research and stakeholder mapping) aims to provide results after a market research and stakeholders analysis to understand which are the trends, segments and customers for the 5GMETA platform, and how the market will evolve in the CCAM market ecosystem. Moreover, a competitor analysis is performed which will be used as input for some deliverables to follow, such as D6.2 (New Business Model), thus creating a value proposition and a business model that better fits the customers and stakeholders needs. The work also identifies the key stakeholders that take part in use cases, which enriches the analysis by showing opportunities and barriers in such an innovative and technological context.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Project intro

5GMETA is an H2020 project running from 1 September 2020 to 31 August 2023 and deployed by a consortium of 11 partners.

Cars capture and generate huge volumes of data in real-time about the driving dynamics, the environment, and the driver and passengers' activities. With greater proliferation of connected and automated mobility applications, the value of data from vehicles is getting strategic, not just for the automotive industry, but also in a wider scope, and it is not limited to the on-board systems and services.

5GMETA open platform aims to leverage car-captured data to stimulate, facilitate and feed them to innovative products and services. As a result, 5GMETA will empower the automotive ecosystem from industry players to new entrants, such as SMEs and high-tech start-ups, granting access to interoperable car-captured data according to data licenses. The access to data coming from relevant geographical regions will generate new opportunities and business models coming from valuable services, where data liability and billing will rely on accountability dashboard of dataflow subscription and volume consumption.

5GMETA expands 5G network functions to enable data monetization thanks to its features such as Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), also called Extreme Mobile Broadband (xMBB), Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications (URLLC), and Massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC) [30]. 5GMETA in addition provides a secure and private pipeline that manages data computing, data flows according to service subscriptions and geographic queries.

5GMETA will realise demonstrators covering different corners in terms of data heterogeneity, value creation and business models to ensure that a wide palette of interests and requirements of third parties and new players are considered beyond traditional automotive industries.

5GMETA will focus on technology transfer activities performing different dissemination initiatives, tutorials and hackathons in synergy with incubators and clusters to capture the attention of SMEs and high-tech start-ups towards a platform leading to new opportunities in an incoming profitable market.

1.2 Purpose of the deliverable

This deliverable, the first one within WP6 *NEW MARKET ECOSYSTEM*, has as overall objective to put in place the necessary building blocks to analyse the CCAM market ecosystem as a basis to build the 5GMETA business model(s) to be compiled in D6.2. In work packages WP2-WP5, the 5GMETA platform is being built and demonstrated in three representative use cases. Under WP6, several actions will be taken to create new business opportunities for new actors, leveraging the results from WP2-WP5. Task 7.4 will design the commercialization strategy for the 5GMETA platform.

This deliverable aims at delivering a first analysis of the current mobility market, and the role of different stakeholders mapped considering the work done in the first year of the project. Indeed, **a second version of this deliverable will be produced at the end of 5GMETA project (M36)** with the final picture of the market addressable by the platform.

Deliverable D6.1 is a first outcome of the work done under Task 6.1, devoted to extract and analyse information relevant to the CCAM industry and to support sound strategy definition in terms of market opportunities, penetration, and development. Specifically, task 6.1 analyses the market for the proposed use cases and aims at identifying key stakeholders that take part in each one. Thus, the present deliverable is intended to be a guide on a preliminary market research and stakeholder analysis, **giving a methodology and an overview of which are the market segments and how the**

market will evolve based on industry key trends, in the context of the 5GMETA project. The deliverable also aims to identify who are the general stakeholders, mainly focusing on the use case stakeholders through the interest/power matrix developed to keep track of end-user needs and to ensure that the planned work fits and adapts to the constantly moving targets concerning innovation in the market.

1.3 Intended audience

The intended audience of this deliverable is people interested in understanding the reference markets for the 5GMETA platform. Furthermore, this deliverable will analyse the main players in the CCAM data collection arena identifying the main stakeholders.

1.4 Structure of the deliverable and its relationship with other work packages/deliverables

The Deliverable D6.1 – Market Research and Stakeholder analysis, is organized as follows:

Chapter 1 – Introduction, briefly presents 5GMETA and describes the purpose of the document and its intended audience.

Chapter 2 – 5GMETA overview and offerings, describes the technology and features involved in the project and also those that are taken into account in the market analysis.

Chapter 3 – Market analysis, provides results about the global megatrends and the market forecasting, exogenous factors that 5GMETA has to take into account to be prepared in terms of market strategy. Finally, a list of competitors and their relationship with the 5GMETA platform from the competitive advantage point of view.

Chapter 4 – Use cases' market intelligence, briefly presents the three Use Cases of the 5GMETA project giving an insight into their market opportunities as well as their barriers.

Chapter 5 - Stakeholder analysis, shows the results of the analysis of the involved stakeholders, highlighting the stakeholders per use case. Lastly, the interest/power matrix is provided.

Chapter 6 - Connection with 5GMETA's technical work

It is important mentioning that D6.1 is the first WP6 deliverable, and it will prepare the floor for the subsequent tasks that will base their work upon the market research analysis outcomes given in this document. Figure 1 graphically represents the involved Work Packages, and which are the tasks related to this deliverable. More in details the tasks are:

- WP2: basically, the first three deliverables have been used as input for D6.1. Please, refer to Section 6 for more details.
- T6.2 *New business models fostered by 5G technologies innovation*: In this task new CAM business models will be found, that could be exploited by new actors and markets thanks to the possibilities brought by 5G connectivity and autonomous driving.
- T6.3 *Activities with Incubators, high-tech start-ups and SMEs in Hackathons*: There, results obtained in D6.1 will be used during Hackatons/testfests and other related activities that will be organised with business incubators, to engage new actors in the business possibilities offered by the 5GMETA platform
- T6.4 *Market outreach plan*: The market outreach plan will target the new markets identified in task T6.1, with the objective of defining a strategy for commercialisation for the new market actors emerged in hackathons and incubators in Task T6.3 and considering the innovative business models described in task T6.2.

- T6.5 *Future plans beyond 5GMETA to catalyse new business opportunities*, to foster a new market ecosystem that will last beyond the life of the 5GMETA project.
- T7.4 *Commercialization Strategy & Exploitation Activities of 5GMETA platform* which will define the commercialisation strategy and will deal with the exploitation activities of the 5GMETA platform as a whole.

Figure 1 Relationship with other work packages

1.5 Main Changes from previous version

The overall structure and the analysis done in this deliverable have been kept also in this new version.

The main changes with respect to the previous version are more related to the relationship of this document and the work done under Task 6.1 with other tasks, the technical work and more in general with the whole project.

More in detail, the main changes are:

- More detailed description of the Purpose of the deliverable along with more information about the relationship with other work packages/deliverables.
- Chapter 2 “5GMETA overview and offerings” has been enriched with more information related to the platform architecture in terms of design principles and relevant requirements. A more detailed description of the 5G role has been added too, focusing the attention on its requirements and standards.
- Added Chapter 6 – “Connection with 5GMETA’s technical work”.
- In the conclusion chapter a draft roadmap for WP6 has been added, and how deliverables are linked to other deliverables and activities.

2 5GMETA OVERVIEW AND OFFERINGS

5GMETA is a project by the European Union, is co-funded by the EU under the H2020 Research and Innovation Programme (grant agreement No. 957360). 5GMETA provides an open platform whose main aim is to collect, analyse and leverage CCAM data so that these data can be used further for the betterment of the automotive ecosystem. The data from the vehicles can be utilized by the stakeholders in the automotive ecosystem to bring new data-driven services, innovative products, and new business models into the market. The motivation for this project is the increasing amount of data generated by vehicles on a daily basis. Collected data are real time data regarding the driving dynamics, the environment, and the driver and passengers' behaviour. These data can be vital in the advancement of not just the automotive industry but also for new players that could enter the market like SMEs and high-tech start-ups. The value creation models of 5GMETA include the generation of revenues, reduction of costs, and improvement of safety and security.

2.1 Design principles

The 5GMETA architecture is designed as an open architecture to allow access to in-vehicle data and resources and to allow the actors in the sector to add, upgrade and swap the architecture components (building blocks). This open architecture aims to allow the development of data markets and compliance to EU laws, mainly, those requesting an open architecture when accessing in-vehicle data. Thus, this architecture shall allow for interoperability, portability, and use of open standards to avoid vendor lock-in [32].

This 5GMETA open architecture embeds many components to ensure security and privacy by design and by default. This is reflected in Task 3.3 work. Therefore, the 5GMETA Sensors & Devices security mechanisms (cryptography, hardening of the Operating Systems in the Vehicles and other devices, regular updates, etc.) and data minimization and the 5G networks will follow EU Toolbox on 5G Security. In this line, edge computing offers a more efficient and secure alternative where data is processed and analyzed closer to the generation point. Furthermore, as the data volumes scale up, a centralized infrastructure is not as effective as a decentralized one could be. Specifically, edge computing gains relevance as it can focus on a local area with almost zero latency and enforcing data privacy. The 5GMETA Platform will use Cloud protocols such as OpenID Connect, OAuth 2.0, WebAuthn, and DIAMETER are envisioned to provide Identity Management, Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting.

Interoperability is also an important design principle of the 5GMETA architecture and will be tested in the different use cases by the 5GMETA consortium and start-ups. Finally, the 5GMETA solution will be manageable by Infrastructure as Code (IaC) to easily deploy, configure, provision, orchestrate, and will use The Organization for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards (OASIS) Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications (TOSCA^{1 2}).

2.2 Technologies involved

The 5GMETA architecture is designed as an open architecture to allow access to in-vehicle data, resources, and the actors in the automotive sector, always being compliant with EU laws. Below a high-level description of the 5GMETA components and how they will work is given; for a deep dive into the architecture see D2.3.

¹ [TOSCA Simple Profile in YAML Version 1.3](#)

² [Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications Version 1.0](#)

The 5GMETA platform embodies four main technological categories: Sensors and Devices, MEC Platform, Cloud Platform, and 5G Network.

Sensors and Devices

The part of sensors and devices belongs to the 5GMETA architecture where all the valuable data is generated and produced, including data coming from both vehicles and Roadside Infrastructure (RDI). The first data source could include data coming from sensors inside the vehicle. Indeed, the vehicle relies on an On-Board Unit (OBU), which is in charge of exchanging and gathering the data generated with the surrounding devices and from the HD camera, radar, LIDAR and all the sensors the vehicle is equipped with. Then, a second source could be the Roadside Unit (RSU), being part of RDI and in charge of overcoming the limited vehicle storage or sharing warning messages such as accidents, and moreover generate other data with its own sensors, e.g. LIDAR, camera and so on. Finally, all these data are sent to the MEC Platform through 5GMETA APIs.

MEC Platform

In the 5GMETA Platform, the MEC Platform plays an intermediary role between Sensors and Devices and the Cloud Platform. The MEC platform is in the proximity of the end-users, in charge of collecting raw data generated by sensors and including secure and private pipelines. Moreover, it includes some computational capabilities, such as filtering, pre-processing, and data collection before sending them to the cloud. It brings flexible computation and privacy capabilities closer to the end-users.

Cloud Platform

The 5GMETA Cloud platform is the core of the 5GMETA architecture. It provides the necessary computing, network and especially streaming functionalities for the road data. It has a twofold objective: on one side, the Cloud platform cooperates with the 5G network and the 5GMETA edge platform previously described; on the other side, the Cloud is the entry point for third party users that interact with the 5GMETA platform. The interaction is provided thanks to open, easy, and flexible Cloud Service APIs.

5G Network

The 5G network is the enabler for the 5GMETA platform. 5G features exploited include network aspects, such as faster communication between nodes in the network, lower latency and so on; but also a newer software point of view in which the network itself and the network functions are virtualized (for further technical details see 5GMETA Deliverable D2.1 “5G requirements & standards” [30]).

2.3 Overview of 5G requirements & standards

The main standards influencing the 5GMETA architecture and an extensive study on the requirements of the CCAM field have been provided in deliverable D2.1 “5G requirements & standards” [30] and D2.2: 5GMETA use cases and their requirements.

3GPP Release 15 provided technical specifications that introduce several new mobile network features that are the basis of the 5th Mobile Network Generation (5G). Among others, the new approach of 5G is to make the network modular and to detach the network functionalities from the underlying hardware using the concept of virtualization.

The goal is to achieve a flexible infrastructure that can be adapted for different scopes while providing reliability and performance. Specifically, data rate, latency, energy efficiency, traffic capacity, and connection density are all key aspects whose performance is boosted in 5G mobile networks.

5G is not only related to the improved performances of the New Radio but several technologies like Network Function Virtualization, Multi-Access Edge Computing, Predictive Quality of Service, Time-

sensitive networking, Network slicing, and Precise Positioning are the main new features that characterize 5G mobile networks and that allow achieving the desired network performance.

The communication requirements that should be guaranteed to satisfy several different vehicular cases in the CCAM field have been explored taking as references the 3GPP [33] [34] technical reports and specifications, and 5GAA white papers [35] [36]. These documents identified requirements for vehicular applications. They provided both general and specific requirements that are related to a given vehicular application. It is indeed complex to define precise requirements that are valid for a wide set of different use cases. The scope of the application, the automation level that should be employed, the type of data to be sent and the scenario of applications are all aspects that strongly influence the requirements.

The identified general requirements are about network management aspects such as upload and download link management, or the number of users to be supported simultaneously. Specific requirements are instead defined considering the following metrics: Latency, Amount of information exchanged, Reliability, Vehicle density, and Vehicle speed.

Use cases related to road safety and to autonomous driving are the most demanding since they require very low latencies (few ms) and high reliability (99,999%) as was detailed in D2.1 “5G requirements & standards” [30]. The amount of information exchanged is instead critical only in those scenarios in which the sharing of sensors’ data is expected. In those cases, an upload bandwidth from a few Mbps up to hundreds of Mbps may be required. Driver-aware services, such as in-vehicle entertainment, are also expected to require significant values for the download bandwidth. Traffic management use cases need to deal with scalability aspects, while they typically do not demand high bandwidth, low latency, or high reliability. Vehicle speed and vehicle density are not strictly related to a specific use case, but they are dependent on the context of the use case. In the highway scenario, high speed and medium vehicle density are expected, while in the urban scenario very high density and low speed are likely.

The use of 5G is pivotal to achieve the performances needed for the realization of the most complex use cases and also to allow the 5GMETA platform to reach its goal of a scalable, reliable, and flexible data collection from vehicles and other road actors.

2.3.1 5G features

The features of the 5G technology are numerous and have been analysed in 5GMETA Deliverable 2.1 “5G requirements & standards” [30]. A brief description of the 5G features, along with information about their relevance within the 5GMETA project is provided in Table 1 below.

Table 1 5G features and their relevance to 5GMETA

5G Features	Description	Relevance for 5GMETA
C-V2X	C-V2X is a cellular technology adapted for connected vehicles communication. It covers communication between vehicles, and other road users or elements by using the cellular network (so called, Vehicle to Network –V2N-communication), but also direct communication (either Vehicle to Vehicle -V2V-, Vehicle to Infrastructure –V2I-, or Vehicle to Pedestrians -V2P).	<u>Medium/low:</u> The main dataflow in 5GMETA involves data moved from vehicles to cloud services, thus the side link communications will not be an essential technology for 5GMETA. Furthermore, the low bandwidth provided by PC5 communications (at least for the initial release) could limit its utilization to some data types and sampling rates.
Software Defined Networking (SDN)	It is one of 5G technologies that allow network virtualisation, needed to provide the flexibility	<u>Medium/high:</u> SDN technology is key for 5GMETA platform as it allows to

5G Features	Description	Relevance for 5GMETA
	required for 5G network architecture. SDN describes a network architecture that allows a completely software-based network management.	manage the network to dynamically and automatically configure a network infrastructure to accommodate the data demand of different use cases to the network resources.
Network Virtualization (NFV)	Function NFV allows to build a network architecture that uses technologies widely adopted in IT virtualization, to virtualize all the existing (and new) network node functions. The dynamic establishment of network services is achieved by an orchestrator capable of deploying VNFs in shared hosting infrastructures and combining them with other services to produce complex network services to support whatever applications and tenants.	High: 5GMETA assets at the network edge will be based on the automated deployment, configuration, and management of VNFs providing specialized features such as data formatting or resampling, processing of data flows to produce actionable data, and the presence of APIs to help developers in the management of data and to ease the implementation of new high-valuable applications.
Multi-access Computing (MEC)	Edge MEC is a new paradigm that provides computing, storage, and in general networking resources within the edge of the network. MEC servers are deployed on a generic computing hardware, and allow for delay-sensitive, highly scalable, and context-aware applications to be executed near the end users.	High: 5GMETA considers MEC as one of the main building blocks of its architecture, focusing on its use in the operators' network. Moreover, APIs relevant to 5GMETA are presented in MEC 013 [1] that describes the Location APIs, useful to access the UE position as known by the network.
Predictive QoS	To address the downfall of the mobile nature of end-users (delivered Quality of Service may vary through time and space, due to a lack of network coverage, resources, or a sudden peak in demand), cellular technology opted for a reactive approach, where the network will report changes in terms of QoS to end-user applications, forcing them to react and make adaptations.	Medium/high: This feature is relevant for 5GMETA as it is fully aligned to meet the business and performance trade-off and to ensure SLAs.
Time Sensitive Networking (TSN)	TSN is a key technology for system synchronization when delivering timing in distributed systems while keeping low latency. Moreover, reliable, and secure transport of data in a	Medium/low: This technology is relevant for 5GMETA for time synchronization to check data timestamps for normalised origin and destination clocks

5G Features	Description	Relevance for 5GMETA
	timely manner is one of the key requirements for real-time and time-critical services and applications.	and to benchmark delivery times essential for real-time and mission-critical applications.
Network slicing	5G network slicing is a network architecture that enables the multiplexing of virtualized and independent logical networks on the same physical network infrastructure [2]. It allows 5G to deal with demand of diverse Quality of Service (QoS) requirements through a 'softwarisation' of the network.	<u>Medium/high:</u> The application of slices to the employed resources is primary since the 5GMETA platform is conceived to deliver different data flows for different services concurrently, to manage heterogeneous SLAs.
Precise positioning	5G allows to retrieve the precise position of devices by means of different positioning functions, specified in the 3GPP TS 38.305 [3]	<u>High:</u> Precise position is an important information for several applications involving vehicles. Position information is exploited by traffic management applications or by applications providing context-aware services to the driver. Moreover, precise positioning is needed for applications involving autonomous driving and road safety information.
Cybersecurity	Security is a key aspect of 5G networks with the softwarisation (NFV, Slicing, SDN) of these networks, the sophistication of cyber-threats, and the reliance on 5G networks as the backbone of modern digital societies.	<u>High:</u> Security is a key aspect of the 5GMETA platform, it is important for the automotive sector where 5G networks will be used for different types of communications and services particularly for data monetization.

2.4 Main offerings

5GMETA design is ready to gather and deliver a vast volume of data. The vehicular data space encompasses data about a vehicle and its surroundings, such as road events and weather conditions. The data can be received directly from a vehicle, from the roadside infrastructure, and from other broad sources of data like a traffic control centre or social media. Data can be static or dynamic.

5GMETA is developed with internationally accepted solutions with collaboration from bodies such as 5GAA, 3GPP, 5G-PPP, ETSI main players for the 5G standards. Some of the proposed features of 5GMETA are as follows:

- Secure and private mass distribution of data from vehicles: The automotive players, the OEM/TIER1, SMEs and high-tech start-ups will be provided with the car data after being ensured privacy, anonymization, along with secure and encrypted access by design.

- Data ownership: The producer of the data like OEMs, suppliers, drivers, or passengers have full control of their data and on the sharing and utilization of them. Data sources are recorded and held accountable with transparency.
- Scalable management: 5GMETA will result in a modular solution that will leverage Service Level Agreements (SLAs) between the suppliers and buyers of data.
- Geo-based range: 5GMETA ensures flexibility of services and applications to be able to consume the data from sources at queried locations, spots, local areas, cities, or countries.
- Data interoperability: The platform will make heterogeneous data and locations homogeneous in terms of structure, schema, and timestamps to ease a universal processing of CCAM services and applications. It will also encourage integration with standards and provide common APIs.
- Real-time data messaging: The platform will establish secure IoT messaging frameworks to develop a global view across the different infrastructures, cars, network, and services co-operating in CCAM applications.
- Flexible business-driven configuration: 5GMETA will provide dashboards to configure service and application subscriptions. The overall accountability of the consumed data is provided with billing, as well as additional performance reports to support decision making.

3 MARKET ANALYSIS

3.1 Global Megatrends

Based on the platform underlying technologies and on the project goals, global megatrends are analysed to give a CCAM market overview focusing on the scope of the 5GMETA platform.

3.1.1 Automotive industry

The automotive industry, since its establishment over a century ago, has undergone numerous changes in terms of policies, technologies, consumer ideologies, and other factors.

The automotive industry, that was once dominated by the United States (US) in the 1900s, has now shifted to a more geographically fragmented market where several countries have adapted their strengths and weaknesses to develop their market.

In Europe, the automotive industry plays a leading role in the prosperity of the region. The turnover generated by the sector accounts for 7% of the region's Gross Domestic Product (GDP)³. It is responsible for providing extensive job opportunities to over 13.8 million people; this figure indicates that around 6.1% of the total employed population is either directly or indirectly working in this industry⁴. According to the European Automobile Manufacturers' Association (ACEA) [4], an organization that represents European car, van, truck, and bus manufacturers, 18.5 million vehicles were manufactured in the European Union in 2019, which represents more than 20% of the global vehicle production.

The early years of the 2010s were able to predict quite accurately the scenario that we are living in today. [7] exhibits a timeline where from the year 2011 to 2015, the onset of the internet revolution within the automotive industry was foreseen. Special attention was given to non-asset-based players entering the market along with a focus on personalisation due to the predicted practice of internet-of-everything. So far, the previous years' analysis has been judicious with the inclusion of a shift in the way of the business models. The analysis carried out in the latter part of the decade concentrates on self-driving cars, seamless communication, and the increasingly dynamic nature of the automotive ecosystem. The trend anticipated from 2020 onwards is the increased localisation instead of globalisation of the market considering the pandemic.

The megatrends that have been obvious worldwide are the advancements in sustainable mobility, the rise of battery electric vehicles, connectivity and digitalization, hybrid electric mobility, and fuel cell mobility. A survey carried out by KPMG's Automotive Institute [7] that includes insights from experts across the automotive sector around the world, exhibits other market trends from 2025 to 2030 like emerging new markets, the establishment of new ecosystems, Mobility-as-a-Service, autonomous and self-driving vehicles, insertion of big data & data monetization, standardisation of modules, downsizing of Internal Combustion Engine (ICE), and digitalization of production in Western Europe.

More anticipated trends could be in clusters, like, European 'Mobility Valley' and employment transition, which means that since Europe can be the future centre for mobility and transport, that will boost employment opportunities. Then, the next cluster will be the decarbonisation of transport of both goods and people, following the zero impact emissions by 2050 policy of sustainable transport. The third cluster will be the formation of new cooperations and alliances as the automotive industry has a lot of technological aspects that are growing further. Hence, the expectations of collaborations within and outside the industry are expected. The fourth cluster will be the future of mobility regulations due to the

³ [Fact about the industry, ACEA](#)

⁴ [Automotive Sector, European Commission](#)

industry moving towards ecosystems and industry need is reducing the complexity and ensuring standardisation [8].

3.1.2 Big data in the automotive industry

The advancement of Big Data has been an evolutionary rather than a revolutionary phenomenon and has drawn a lot of attention. With this much attention, the digital and computing world became hoarder of information about everything that is connected in one way or another to the Internet. In the mid-2010s, over 2 billion people worldwide were connected to the Internet, and over 5 billion individuals owned mobile phones. By 2020, it was predicted that over 50 billion devices would be connected to the Internet. The data production and collection happened at a lightning speed, and today the data produced is almost 44 times more than the data produced in 2009 [9].

The collection of data is not enough, for data to be useful, it needs to undergo processing and analysis so that targeted data can be used for specific purposes. In the late-2010s, 80% of the processing and analysis of data took place in data centres and centralised computing facilities, and 20% in smart connected objects, such as cars, home appliances or manufacturing robots, and in computing facilities close to the user. Today, we are still at the same stage. These proportions are anticipated to be reversed, thanks to edge computing technology, which brings the data processing closer to where the data is needed and applied⁵. This method has proven to be more feasible and sustainable and has also presented opportunities for business to get more control over their data [10].

The European Union has taken this infusion of data thoughtfully and intends to use those data to transform most of the sectors that function within it. The broad aim is to create a sole market for the data gathered. Data is expected to be the way to make the gap among different sectors smaller. Data flow is a priority between different sectors, a way that is beneficial for all actors included in the data exchange. This is to be done under the strict European guidelines related to privacy and data protection. The goal is to establish competition laws, so that the data exchange can happen freely. Accessing data poses challenges such as the rules should be fair, practical, and clear. The same applies for reusing the data. For this to materialize successfully, next generation standards should be established and research for new tools and infrastructure to store and process data needs to be started. The European Union will also come together to have a shared cloud capacity for seamless operations. The Union will also give the users rights, tools and skills, so that data remains under the owners control. As per the reports in February 2020 [12], [10], the European Union will invest through the channels from Digital Europe Programme⁶, The Connecting Europe Facility⁷, and Horizon Europe⁸, a total of €4-6 billion by 2025 in common European data spaces and a European federation of cloud infrastructure and services to achieve a single market for data to make the region more competitive and innovative in terms of processes, products and services.

The progression of data in various industries has been enlightening, but at the same time the infusion of data in the automotive industry has been transforming. An expedited adoption of technologies (such as artificial intelligence, connectivity through sensors, and others) allows the industry to move towards adapting services with the assistance of big data. The ecosystem is seeing a flood of new players, such as technologically advanced companies and the expected industry change can already be seen. The big data market in the automotive industry was valued at USD 3,289.60 million in 2019, and it is expected to reach USD 7,844.01 million by 2025, registering a Compounded Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 16.81% during the period of 2020-2025⁹. The application of big data in the automotive industry is at a nascent stage. Data analytics has been a vital component at the backend of the automotive industry in

⁵ [Edge Computing, Wikipedia](#)

⁶ [Digital Europe Programme](#)

⁷ [The Connected Europe Facility](#)

⁸ [Horizon Europe](#)

⁹ [Global NewsWire, December 2020](#)

the manufacturing, marketing and supply side, but the data from the final products such as passenger cars and commercial vehicles has just emerged.

In Europe, to make the final consumers aware about the values proposed by data in their automobiles, the European Automobile Manufacturers' Association (ACEA) launched a new educational website: www.CarDataFacts.eu¹⁰. The aim of the website is to shed light on the increase in connected vehicles and their use and processing of data. With the rising volume of data and the necessity behind it, the website answers questions like why the sharing of car data can result in benefits for the contributors by pointing out general use cases like avoiding traffic jams, predictive maintenance, easier access to local information like restaurants, smart parking, automatically paying for parking or tolls, emergency services, entertainment, opportunities like tailored insurance services, and making the car and extension of an office or a home. Some other questions the website answers are if the contributor of data can choose the amount of data they share, what kind of data is necessary for sharing, how can the contributor protect their personal data, and the safe and secure ways of sharing car data. The website aims to eliminate the buzz and the confusion regarding car-based data and provide facts and aspects related to the sharing of vehicle-generated data with third parties. Through various educational infographics, the website answers the most common questions about access to car data in a clear and simple way.

European automotive revenues, based on an estimate about how much consumers will spend, are expected to grow from €850 billion in 2016 to €1,400 billion in 2030. Over the same period, the prediction is that the share of data-enabled services and shared mobility will increase from 0.2 to 27 percent of total automotive revenues [8]. Car-generated data will benefit different stakeholders in different ways and will transform the automotive industry into a market which is no longer run by OEMs and TIER1 Suppliers, but also technology companies which can exploit such data.

3.2 Industry Analysis

To understand the factors that are influencing the upcoming technology 5GMETA, an analysis needs to be carried out. The PESTLE (Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal and Environmental) analysis was chosen as it is a situational tool providing resources to analyse the external business environment, which is dynamic in nature. Through the exploration of political, economic, socio-cultural, technological, legal and environmental or ecological factors influencing the market, PESTLE analysis allows one to draw conclusions about the industry attractiveness, the market potential, the future growth, the trends and, in some cases, the key success factors [14]. The PESTLE analysis described in this section is limited to the geographical scope of the European Union.

3.2.1 Political Factors

The automotive industry in Europe is one of the most successful industries. It has strong economic ties to other industrial sectors and has been prone to cause a multiplier effect, which means that the efforts in the automotive industry affect surrounding industries like raw materials, machinery, software, advertising, amongst others. Hence, these ties result in high percentage of deflection in the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of the EU economy. The EU has had solid strategies to enhance the industry with the stable internal market of vehicles, sustainable development, safety plans, and increase of competition for fair trade in the region.

The EU has taken significant steps for the betterment of the industry over the past years. The European Battery Alliance¹¹ launched in October 2017 aims to develop a sustainable battery development value chain in Europe. The alliance accounted for 440 actors and an investment of €100 billion.

¹⁰ [ACEA, 2017](#)

¹¹ [European Battery Alliance, 2017](#)

The EU supports the involvement of advanced technological solutions to promote safer traffic and decreased pollution. The European Commission has proposed new models with advanced safety features to fulfil the long-term goal of achieving zero fatalities and serious injuries by 2050, in a strategy named 'Vision Zero'¹². One of the key strategic indicators that the EU aims to accomplish is the 50% reduction in fatalities and serious injuries by 2030.

The EU is also a frontrunner in the development and application of the automated vehicles market. In May 2018, the European Commission has published the EU strategy¹³ and guidelines¹⁴ for connected and automated mobility. This was done to bring different players across the EU together to achieve harmonisation in this industry sector. These guidelines aim to alert the manufacturers and partners regarding the regulations and ensure that the innovation is carried out safely in accordance with the EU laws.

Measures have also been taken to enhance the competitive scenario of the industry. The European Commission is also focusing on four major areas (namely smart regulation, international harmonisation, bilateral regulatory dialogues, and access to finance and market support for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs)¹⁵) to enhance the competitive scenario of the industry.

The European Commission has begun its transition into realising a Single European Transport Area with a digital layer able to link all the actors and the infrastructures of the transport system. This requires building a digital architecture with common and harmonized standards, interfaces, and open access to data. Thus, the data ecosystem must have proper security and privacy as well. To facilitate this seamlessly across borders, the European Union member states have started setting up their National Access Point¹⁶ (NAP) where the entire data of the country will be available for accessing, reusing, and easy exchanging. The NAPs¹⁷ already set up are available on the European Commission website. These access points are not restricted by their type but can be databases, data warehouses, data marketplaces, repositories, registers, web portals, etc. The availability of these access points can be crucial for the purposes of 5GMETA. Either these data points can act as sources for the 5GMETA platform and be collaborators, or act as competitors from which automotive data can be easily accessible.

The competitiveness and the harmonisation of the environment is paramount for the EU. In 2016, the GEAR 2030¹⁸ group was formed to accelerate a coordinated approach in terms of the growth of the automotive industry. The aim is to overcome challenges faced by the industry due to globalisation, change in mobility patterns, rising expectations of consumers, and digitalisation. With focusing on areas like enhancing the value chain, automated and connected vehicles, the group wants to bring Europe forward with regulatory standards and market access benefits for all.

Harmonisation in the EU is also carried out technically under the Whole Vehicle Type- Approval System (WVTA)¹⁹ where if a country in the EU can obtain a certificate for the deployment of a vehicle, it is valid almost EU-wide. This ensures that the overall system in the EU is seamless, and manufacturers need not face testing multiple times.

¹² [Vision Zero Initiative](#)

¹³ [On the road to automated mobility: An EU strategy for mobility of the future](#)

¹⁴ [Guidelines on the exemption procedure for the EU approval of automated vehicles](#)

¹⁵ [Policy and Strategy in the Automotive Industry, European Commission](#)

¹⁶ [National Access Points, intelligent Transport System](#)

¹⁷ [List of NAPs](#)

¹⁸ [GEAR 2030 Strategy](#)

¹⁹ [Technical Harmonisation in the EU](#)

Overall, the political scenario in Europe faces issues due to the large number of different stakeholders being involved in the regulatory process. Hence, the policies are meticulously tailored around the regulations and agreements, and goals are set for making Europe a world leader again.

3.2.2 Economic Factors

The European economy has been following a long-term diminishing trend and therefore losing its global share. Although in 2019, the GDP of the European Union was 14 trillion euros, as for the global share it was just around 16% and the GDP is expected to fall even further to 14.63% by 2024. Germany is the largest economy, followed by France. The fastest growing economies within Europe are the Republic of Ireland and countries in Eastern Europe. In 2018, there were over 25 million SMEs in the European Union, which contributed more than 4.4 trillion euros to the economy and employed over 97.7 million people [17].

Out of the vehicles manufactured in 2019, around 5.6 million were exported around the globe, this was beneficial as it generated a trade surplus of €74 billion for the EU. The R&D (Research and Development) investments in the sector are one of the highest in EU which goes on the upper limit of €60.9 billion, annually. This figure is approximately 29% of the total spending; 2019 saw an increase in the R&D funding by 6.1%. Europe also leads the world in patents for self-driving vehicles, adding up to 33.3% of all applications. Automotive industry is also a significant source of government revenue, bringing in over €440.4 billion in taxes [4].

The automotive industry also attracts investors, such as technology companies from other industry sectors. Automotive and mobility start-ups, since 2010 have received more than €100 billion [8].

3.2.3 Socio-Cultural Factors

External factors also include the social and the cultural perspectives that influence the market. Knowing what factors are driving consumer demands on a macro-scale can allow sellers to fit into the perspective and increase the number of sales. The diversity of people in Europe is an asset for the companies operating in the region. People yearn for the freedom that comes from mobility and, with the years, the mobility in Europe is becoming time efficient, safer, and more affordable. Out of all the journeys that are made, 70% are made by private vehicles and over 55% of journeys in the public transport area are made by bus. Average costs per kilometre have decreased by 65% for private cars in the past 40 years and has hence promoted individual mobility [8].

The consumer mind set has seen a shift over the past few years with regards to environmental awareness and sustainability. As a consequence, the overall demand for electric vehicles has increased. Over 55% of all new car sales predicted by Koster, Kuhnert and Stürmer [18] could be fully electrified by 2030. Consumers are willing to move towards alternative powertrain technologies given that it means sustainable future for the industry. With the future prospect of highly innovative aspects such as autonomous vehicles, shared vehicles and the use of data for mobility, the demographic can see a shift, as the younger generation (people under 40 years old) is more likely to buy advanced vehicles.

With the influx of electric vehicles the market is about to become more fragmented and localised. Different mobility concepts have been applied to different mobility areas such as urban and rural. As the distances of travel changes, consumers are more likely to change the way they travel. This also applies to dense areas such as cities where parking space is scarce and shared mobility is preferred, while at the same time fuel-efficient cars are preferred by a consumer who commutes from suburban areas to the urban areas for work. In addition, on-demand, door-to-door mobility will be common in these cities by 2050. For the population living in rural areas, individual mobility needs to be enhanced with improving the fuel consumption and making the use of more eco-friendly vehicles through better fuel access [8].

Personal attitudes regarding the ownerships of assets also influence the consumer mind set. Cars are not just a commodity, but large division of the population stills considers them as a social status, and in some cases a fashion accessory. It is seen as a possession that people use to flaunt their net worth and

wealth. The ownership of an automobile, and which segment it is coming from, is a demonstration of income. Growing disposable incomes in developing and already developed countries help facilitate this.

3.2.4 Technological Factors

The automotive industry is rapidly transforming itself with the assistance of up-coming technologies such as data-enabled services, Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS), alternative powertrains, cloud-based mobility services, big data monetization, digitalization, and more. The market is highly dynamic as the advances in technology are causing a shift in the way the industry functions. The major evolutions in the automotive sector are reflected by the acronym ACES, which stands for: Autonomous driving, Connectivity, Electrification, and Shared mobility. An average vehicle is nowadays a mix of mechanical, software and electronics engineering. Electronics, electrical components and software has become an integral competence. It is predicted that by 2030 25% of the vehicle value will consist of electronics and 30% of the vehicle value will depend on its software [8].

Standards for 5G are being developed by multiple bodies including 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF), European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI), International Telecommunication Union (ITU). 3GPP²⁰ is an international body made up of seven telecommunications standard development organizations. 3GPP focuses on 5G studies of next-generation architecture, the 5G New Radio (NR), enhanced mobile broadband, ultra-reliability and low latency, frequency ranges, and the importance of forwarding compatibility in radio and protocol design. The United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE)²¹, in accordance with the CARS21 communication²², works on global industry standards for automotive, safety and environmental protection.

As for the future, 80% of the top 10 OEMs are working towards building autonomous vehicles. Connected trucks are expected to make up around 80% of the entire fleet by 2030. Shared mobility has already made a place for itself in the market with the companies like BlaBlaCar and others, and as of today €55 billion have already been invested in ride-sharing start-ups. Electric vehicles are highly demanded because of their advantages for the environment and cost-effectiveness in terms of fuel/energy costs ratio. The sale of electric vehicles is expected to be around 6 million vehicles per year by 2030 [8].

According to a report by McKinsey & Company (2020) [21], the development of autonomous vehicles is divided into 6 levels (0 to 5). Levels 0, 1 and 2 fall under the Advanced Driver-Assistance Systems (ADAS). Level 0 is no automation, level 1 is characterised by driver assistance steering merged with the system and human driver, and some driving modes. Level 2 involves partial automation, where the system takes care of the steering execution, acceleration, and deceleration but monitoring, and dynamic driving is taken care of by the human. The levels 3, 4 and 5 fall under the Autonomous Driving (AD), where the system has full control over steering, acceleration, deceleration, and monitoring of driving environment. Level 3 is conditional automation wherein dynamic driving task is only carried by humans. Level 4 is defined as high automation with system taking control of everything but has space for only some driving modes. Finally, level 5 corresponds to the full automation with everything controlled by the system in all driving modes and situations. According to such report, level 2 features will be the main growth driver until 2025 with a 47% market share for the level 2 entry, while level 2 advanced will hold a share of 12%. Level 3 will hold a relatively smaller share of 4%. By 2030, the total market share increase of autonomous vehicles is expected to rise by 4% with level 2 autonomous vehicles having a predicted market share of 39% for the entry version and 17% for the advanced version. Levels 3 and 4 of autonomous vehicles will hold a share of 5% and 3%, respectively. It is expected that as the levels 3

²⁰ [3rd Generation Partnership Project \(3GPP\)](#)

²¹ [UNECE, European Commission](#)

²² [CARS 21 Communication](#)

and 4 of autonomous vehicles enter the market, their less technologically adept counterparts of level 2 autonomous vehicles will lose their market share gradually.

Europe is the birthplace of the automobile and technological innovation has been consistently happening in the region over the years. In addition, over 8,700 automotive patents were granted by the European Patent Office in 2017 but a reduction was seen in the year 2018 with 5,848 patents. Till 2018, Europe was leading with a global market share of 33.3 % for self-driving vehicle related patents [5]. The brisk evolution of technologies in the automotive industry has made the industry prone to disruption. The circulation of autonomous vehicles is expected to be about 15% by 2030 and this will change the way the cars are in use today. The cars will be more similar to an environment where drivers can spend time while focusing their attention on other vital things than 'keeping their eyes on the road' [22].

The 5G technology is expected to be a key enabler for reliable communication for vehicles, managing their safety, and automation. 5G features like network slicing, C-V2X communications or edge computing will play a major role in changing the automotive industry. An increase in the number of sensors on-board vehicles and an increase in the number of vehicles will both require a network with high capacity for efficient functioning. 5G will also speed up the processing times for D2D (device to device) communications thanks to extremely low latencies. With the requirements that 5G technology is expected to fulfil, a stable automotive ecosystem can be expected in the coming years [23].

3.2.5 Legal Factors

The European region consists of several countries, due to which it is important to establish synchronization and standardization rules across borders. The legislative environment follows stringent measures for the coordination, healthy and fair competition, movement of different types of vehicles across borders, environmental considerations, to name a few. The rigidity of the rules plays a vital role in the stable functioning of the market.

The European Commission has developed policies like 'Europe on the move'²³ for safe, clean, connected, and automated mobility. The most recent regulations (EU)2021/133 and (EU)2018/858²⁴ focus on the exchange of data that takes place in the automotive ecosystem. In relation to standardisation, they address which data format should be used. Legislations are in place to control the emissions and fuel consumption from vehicles in all categories. Market approval of vehicles circulating all over Europe has specific laws in place depending upon whether they are motorized vehicles, two or three-wheel vehicles or quadricycles, tractors, and non-road mobile machinery. For manufacturers to launch vehicles on the market, they need to be meticulous about the rules on components, environment, and type approvals²⁵.

Data sharing and control over data has been a debated topic in the EU. The OEMs use the 'Extended Vehicle Concept' to transmit and store data from the car to the servers of the OEMs themselves giving them a monopolistic control of the data. The automotive ecosystem can benefit from the sharing of this data for services to car owners and drivers. To remove the OEMs monopoly, policy discussions such as a non-discriminatory government solution on a.o. a shared server for the vehicle data access, or an on-board application platform to control the in-vehicle access and management of data can be considered [24].

The main applicable laws regarding data protection in the automotive sector in the EU are described in a guideline document [14], which addresses in depth the processing of data in the context of connected vehicles and mobility related applications. These are:

²³ [Europe on the move, European Commission](#)

²⁴ [Regulation \(EU\) 2021/133](#)

²⁵ [Legislation, European Commission](#)

- The EU legal framework is the General data protection regulation (GDPR) (2016/679), which is applicable in all cases of personal data collection and processing in the context of connected vehicles.
- The ePrivacy Directive (2002/58/EC, as revised by 2009/136/EC), which fixes a specific standard for all actors who wish to store or access information that is stored in the servers of a subscriber or a user in the European Economic Area (EEA). The ePrivacy Directive contains provisions that apply to the providers of publicly available data of electronic communication services and providers of the public communication networks. This directive applies to any entity that stores or reads information from a technical equipment without the knowledge of the type of data being stored or accessed. Hence, the connected vehicle and every device connected to it will be considered as a terminal equipment (for example, smartphone, computer), and the provisions of ePrivacy directive will be applied where relevant.

The European Data Protection Board (EDPB) pointed out the interaction between GDPR and ePrivacy Directive in 5/2019. The ePrivacy Directive mentions that prior consent is required for storing information or gaining access to the information that is already stored in the terminal equipment of a subscriber or a user.

3.2.6 Environmental Factors

The European region has been one of the frontrunners in adapting the environmental regulations in the automotive industry. The evolution of climate change patterns has been a growing concern along with pollutants from vehicles. With rising awareness, the European Union took major steps to tackle this problem. The main aim is to reduce the emission of CO₂, NO₂ and particulate matter along with a focus on noise reduction and elimination of greenhouse gases. Vehicles are a major cause of the growth of greenhouse gas emissions, especially CO₂, which contributes around 15% of the EU's emissions. The European Commission strives to reduce emissions from light-duty vehicles, heavy-duty vehicles, and mobile machinery²⁶. Another key objective is to start using alternative fuels. By 2025, the European Commission plans to install about 1 million public recharging and refuelling stations for the 13 million zero-emission and low-emission vehicles that are expected to be in use²⁷.

Under the European Green Deal²⁸, the EU wants to achieve neutrality in the emission of greenhouse gases by 2050 and overall make the EU economy sustainable in the process. The European Climate Law²⁹ goes together with the deal by giving economies involved a guideline on how to invest in environmentally friendly technologies, support green innovation, circulation of cleaner, cheaper forms of public and private transport, decarbonising the energy sector, sustainable construction, and work on global environmental standards. The EU will also provide financial support to the member states that struggle with this new initiative. With the COP21 Paris Agreement³⁰, new regulations like (EU) 2019/631³¹ for setting a limit on CO₂ emission performance standards for new passenger cars and for new vans are being set in the EU. In addition to this, 20 member states offer incentives to owners of electric vehicles such as bonus payments and premiums³².

Overall, the environmental regulations have been working. The average new car emits 123g CO₂/km. CO₂ emissions from new cars are down by 20% since 2008. Almost 70% of all new cars emit less than 130g CO₂/km and CO₂ emissions per car produced dropped by 38% between 2005 and 2019 [5].

²⁶ [Environment Protection, European Commission](#)

²⁷ [Sustainable Transport, European Commission](#)

²⁸ [European Green Deal](#)

²⁹ [European Climate Law](#)

³⁰ [The Paris Agreement](#)

³¹ [Regulation \(EU\) 2019/631](#)

³² [Electric Vehicles: Tax benefits and Purchase incentives](#)

3.3 Competitors Analysis

There are over 153³³ connected vehicle platforms on the market, globally. Their offerings differ in scale and number of services, everything is centred around data and how the platform processes these data. Based on data, a connected car platform builds its capabilities depending on its resources and partnerships. For the competitor analysis, vehicle data marketplaces based in Europe are chosen. The analysis is based on desk research on the internet. A basic search on Google³⁴ about data marketplaces yields results about the start-ups as well as the established companies. Further information was obtained from industry reports and websites such as Crunchbase³⁵, Owler³⁶. Data marketplaces are platforms where users can buy and sell data. A marketplace is a way for data providers to market, manage and sell their data. In turn, data marketplaces allow data buyers to browse, compare and purchase data from multiple sources collected in one, easy-to-navigate marketplace [28]. These marketplaces originated either in Europe or somewhere else and are functioning in Europe. The companies/projects collect data from several data sources, process it, and make it available to further use by other parties. All competitors considered are OEMs' independent platforms or marketplaces and earn their revenues by leveraging these data.

Several companies, joint ventures, vertical solutions and projects were considered in the process of selecting the competitors. Below is the list of indirect competitors that were discarded from the direct competitors list:

- BlackBerry IVY³⁷: This is joint venture by BlackBerry and Amazon Web Services to create a scalable, cloud-connected software platform to be used by automakers to leverage data for the creation of personalized driver and passenger experiences and improve operations of connected vehicles. The platform is focused on the benefit of automakers and auto suppliers with advantages like innovation for customer experiences, new revenue stream and business models, cost reduction from processing data, improved operations and expansion of their ecosystems. Although BlackBerry IVY is an intelligent vehicle data platform, it is built solely for the benefit of automakers, OEMs which want to develop a connected platform for themselves, and their drivers and riders. It is not a data marketplace with free access to data for several entities and hence is an indirect competitor.
- Aeris Mobility Suite³⁸: This is an IoT-enabled platform that offers connectivity and product development services. Aeris mobility suite offers an opportunity to build and monetize from connected vehicles. It offers solutions for sectors like healthcare, fleet telematics, cold chain monitoring, etc. Aeris mobility suite encourages car companies to transform themselves into technology companies and develop a connected vehicle program within 6 months, build customer loyalty, and deploy applications within 90 days. The suite is focused for the automakers and auto suppliers and does not count as a platform which anyone can access and use data from it. Hence, it remains an indirect competitor.
- Mojo platform³⁹: Mojo designs, develops, and delivers connected mobility solutions that transform data into scalable services for their partners and their customers. They have products like the connected mobility platform, fleet management solution, a solution for mobile network operators and one for automakers. The company originated in Canada and has been running operations in the USA. The major presence is outside Europe and hence the company has not been considered for the direct competitor analysis. Mojo has modular solutions for automakers who want to scale up as data-driven

³³ [Big data for connected car platforms, Intellias](#)

³⁴ [Google](#)

³⁵ [Crunchbase](#)

³⁶ [Owler](#)

³⁷ [BlackBerry IVY](#)

³⁸ [Aeris](#)

³⁹ [Mojo](#)

services providers for their customers and gain profit from them. Since Mojio is not a marketplace which encourages the exchange of data without constraints, it is considered as an indirect competitor.

- Airlinq⁴⁰: This is a private company focused on the acceleration, development and deployment of large scale connected applications around smart mobility and ecosystem monetization for automakers, mobile network operators and consumers around the world. It has a range of products like Autolinq, which is a connected car platform for the automotive industry, and Mobilinq which provides IoT connectivity for business operations. The Autolinq connected car platform is built for automakers to extend digital services to their customers and secure dynamic connectivity. Autolinq encourages its customers, who are OEMs to use data from their customer to scale up their operations in the digital services area. Since it is not a marketplace and the utilization of data is limited to the OEMs who are the customers of Autolinq, it is not a direct competitor.
- Microsoft Connected Vehicle Platform (MCVP)⁴¹: The platform is a digital base on which OEMs can deliver value-added services to their customers. MCVP platform is built upon Microsoft Azure, which is a cloud computing platform by the company. The partnerships include automotive companies like Volkswagen, Renault-Nissan- Mitsubishi Alliance and companies from other industries like TomTom, Telenav, Tata communications, Otonomo, WirelessCar, Cubic Telecom, etc. Major use cases include in-vehicle experiences, navigation, customer engagement, insights, feedback, telematics and prediction services, connectivity and over the air updates. The main trends that follow MCVP are:
 - Mobility as a Service: Ride hailing, ride sharing, air taxis, autonomous drone fleets, micro-mobility services. Other examples like traffic-based routing, weather reports, planning trips, and inclusion of digital assistants to support end-to-end mobility also fall into this category.
 - Connecting vehicles to the cloud: This enables over-the-air updates via phone apps.
 - Delivering value from the cloud to vehicles and phones: With 5G constant high-speed connectivity is expected.

Microsoft intends to create an ecosystem with the involvement of brands from all sectors like automotive, telecommunications and software, but the data exchange and intelligence is dependent only on the members of the ecosystem and not available for new companies like start-ups. Hence, it is considered as an indirect competitor.

- Ericsson Connected Vehicle Cloud⁴²: This is the cloud platform developed by Ericsson to create more opportunities for OEMs and their relationship with their customers. Since the vehicles are more software defined than hardware, the cloud can use data from the vehicles to create new revenue streams for vehicles that are owned and shared. Some use cases include vehicle telematics, fleet management, service innovation, universal connectivity, and assisted driving. Key Points covered by Ericsson Connected Vehicle Cloud include:
 - A cloud execution platform: For the innovation of new services and the possibility to continuously deploy and enhance them.
 - Security: OEMs can use the vehicle data to access new services, establishing a secure connected between drivers and their vehicle interaction, sharing of personal data.
 - A global scale of connectivity.
 - Guaranteed Service Level Agreements for platform solutions, through 24/7 operation and maintenance services.

⁴⁰ [Airlinq](#)

⁴¹ [Microsoft Connected Vehicle Platform](#)

⁴² [Ericsson Connected Vehicle Cloud](#)

Ericsson has a connected vehicle cloud as an ecosystem with 41 million vehicles across 130 countries. It also has 5G ready use cases, but the entire service and the platform is limited to vehicle manufacturers, suppliers, and service providers who are a part of the ecosystem. Hence, it is considered as an indirect competitor.

- Amazon Web Services (AWS) Connected Vehicle Solution⁴³: This enables automotive manufacturers and suppliers to build IoT applications on a cloud platform to collect, process, analyse data without the need to manage the infrastructure. The connected vehicle solution is built upon AWS solution, which itself extends services to several industries. The service is limited to automotive manufacturers and suppliers and is not a data marketplace, hence it is not a direct competitor.

The above list highlights the potential competitors, but most of them only focus on the benefits for the OEMs and TIER1 suppliers. Below direct competitors of 5GMETA are listed, competitors which are neutral vehicle data marketplaces and are not advantageous solely to just one stakeholder of the automotive ecosystem.

- Automat Project⁴⁴: This is a project funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 programme. The project lasted three years and ended building a prototype and publishing some research papers. The project was designed to be an open ecosystem for manufacturers of vehicles and service providers. Independent vehicle data is made available at single point of data access via a marketplace. It defines standardized and open interfaces for unconstrained data access. Automat converts the vehicle data into a harmonized and generic format called Common Vehicle Information Model (CVIM). Automat includes the provision of mechanisms to guarantee data security, integrity, and privacy.
- Otonomo⁴⁵: The Otonomo Automotive Data Services Platform is a private company that collects vehicle and fleet related data on a global scale. The company collects, secures, cleanses, normalizes, aggregates and improves car data from multiple sources to be provided to the customers of the marketplace. It delivers datasets that can directly be used by the application developers and eliminates a significant amount of development time and effort for apps and services based on connected car data.
- Wejo⁴⁶: This is a private company that collects vehicle and related data from automotive manufacturers. Their aim is to organize and enhance streams of authentic connected vehicle data in a way that it creates value for the customer. Wejo data and insights are licensed to its customers. Wejo specializes in in-vehicle data and processes billions of data points from thousands of sensors globally. Wejo analyses this data and makes it accessible to create customer and economic value.
- Caruso⁴⁷: This is a private company that provides a neutral and open data and service marketplace where data suppliers in all sectors can take part offering both their telematics and complementary data to the aftermarket. It can be referred to as a mobility data marketplace, which enables users to use data across multiple vehicle manufacturers. The data brokerage is the enablement of a connected vehicle aftermarket. It includes a brokering engine, which handles tasks like data ingest and streaming as well as transactional billing and logging.

These competitors are considered the most relevant for 5GMETA and will be further analysed and compared to 5GMETA in the second version of this document.

⁴³ [Amazon Web Services \(AWS\) Connected Vehicle Solution](#)

⁴⁴ [Automat Project](#)

⁴⁵ [Otonomo](#)

⁴⁶ [Wejo](#)

⁴⁷ [Caruso Dataplace](#)

3.4 Conclusion

In this section, market analysis has been performed considering the evolution of the market under the Global Megatrend section. Additionally, an analysis of the segment has been performed at which the 5GMETA project tends to be positioned, the Automotive industry and the usage of Big Data. Moreover, a PESTLE analysis allowed us to understand which are the external business factors that could impact the current project. In the end, some competitors that are already approaching the same envisioned market segment as the 5GMETA project were presented, highlighting to which extent and why they can be considered as direct or indirect competitors.

The analysis allows to define some key concepts in a highly innovative environment, where both the number of connected vehicles and the generated information will exponentially grow in the next years. To get a realistic idea of the number of vehicles that could be connected to the 5GMETA platform, it is important to define the size of the market. The size and growth of the market will be estimated in the next version of this deliverable benchmarked for the following years: 2023, 2025, and 2030. In the Global Megatrend section, we have pointed out how much effort the European Union puts into this continuously growing sector, which allows us envisioning the future market in the automotive and big data sectors. Therefore, there are plenty of possibilities for 5GMETA to penetrate the market in a disruptive way, exploiting the megatrend and driver in such a market.

Indeed, for a better understanding of how 5GMETA can be placed in the market, a PESTLE analysis clarified the key external factors. Some of the external business factors that could impact the 5GMETA project have been described. First, the Political factor has been addressed, as the EU strategy influences the market in the automotive sector and enhances the competitiveness of the industry, but also faces issues due to a large number of countries which determines the huge impact that EU has on the 5GMETA project in terms of regulation, agreements and goals. Then, the analysis moved on to Economical, Technological, Socio-cultural, Legal and Environmental factors. All of them contributed to have a clear vision of exogenous variables that have to be taken into account, informing us about the value proposition and having the capability to strategically change it regarding the economical dynamics and compliance with the legal factor. Both influence the customer segment, their needs and what the project create as value and what it delivers to the user.

Finally, a competitor analysis gave us a first overview of how the market is populated and which are the real and running business models. Some big companies have been found such as AWS, in partnership with Blackberry or with its own platform, Microsoft, Ericsson; but also other minor private companies. It comes out that the former big companies focus on the benefit of OEMs and TIER1 suppliers, without giving much importance to the value created from data and thus can be considered as indirect competitors. The latter set of competitors include minor companies whose business model puts them in the same market segment as 5GMETA. These competitors are considered as the more relevant to 5GMETA and will be further analysed and compared in the second version of this deliverable.

4 USE CASES' MARKET INTELLIGENCE

Use cases' market intelligence is one of the core actions of Task 6.1 “*Market research and stakeholder mapping*”, which aims at analysing the market for the proposed use cases and identifying key stakeholders that take part in each one. Within D 2.2 “5GMETA use cases and their requirements” [30], an initial draft of all possible use case categories related to the 5GMETA platform has been provided, as reported in Figure 2, while Table 2 reports a brief description of them.

Figure 2 Use Case categories by 5GMETA

Table 2 Use case categories from D2.1

Use cases categories	Description
Road safety	This category includes all those use cases that can enhance the road safety either by alerting the driver or by actively intervening.
Cooperative driving	Use cases related to autonomous driving in which autonomous vehicles interact and cooperate to manage complex traffic manoeuvres (e.g., cooperative overtaking, cooperative intersection crossing).
Driver comfort	Use cases related to the improvement of the driving experience (e.g., GLOSA, parking service).
Vehicle status monitoring	Use cases implementing predictive maintenance services and other services based on the status of the vehicle.
Traffic management	In this category there are all those use cases related to the management of traffic flows at macroscopic level (e.g., management of the traffic flows in a city).
Road infrastructure planning	Use cases related to planning and design of road infrastructure in a long-term view (e.g., modification of a crossing, upgrading of a motorway).

Use cases categories	Description
Driver-aware services	In this category, the use cases provide services related to the specific driver preferences and behaviours (e.g., driver coaching, usage-based insurance) and to in-vehicle entertainment services.

Since the 5GMETA project is in an early stage in terms of implementation, it is possible to derive a detailed market intelligence applied to each of those use cases. In the following, the market intelligence will be applied to the three use cases demonstrated within the deliverable. Thus, based on the market analysis results, here the use cases' market research which will be used to make a first draft of market opportunities and market barriers along with a first draft of potential business models for each Use case.

Each use case's chapter is structured as follows:

- Use case motivation
- High-level description of the use case
- Potential business models
- Market opportunity
- Market barriers

The sub-section 2 "*High-level description of the use case*" is a summary of the more detailed and comprehensive use case description that can be found in Deliverable 2.2 "*5GMETA use cases and their requirements*" [31], where additional information can be found such as requirements, KPIs, etc. Thus, for the readers interested in more details or who are already aware of how use cases work, they can skip the sub-section "*High-level description of the use case*" of each use case chapter.

Tables present in the section related to potential Business Models have been already reported in Deliverable D2.2. Here, the tables are reported for completeness and to further analyze those business models in terms of Market opportunity and barriers.

This is a first market intelligence analysis to provide the reader with an overview of the potential market assessment for 5GMETA in those 3 scenarios. The second version of this deliverable will go deeper in detail and will enlarge its scope to other use cases.

4.1 Use Case 1: R&D Live Training Loop

4.1.1 Use case motivation

Different sensors monitor the vehicle's surrounding environment: events related to driving dynamics, road conditions, and the system's performance trigger the Cloud through the MEC. The vehicle's connectivity has to be guaranteed through 5G network by offering low latency and high bandwidth, allowing sending dataset that will be elaborated in the Cloud with a Machine Learning (ML) model.

The motivation for this UC1 is to test and validate safety procedures connected to the response of the function under specific circumstances or scenarios. The test approach depends on internal signals of the vehicle, the environment outside, the driver and other road participants.

Two scenarios are targeted in the present use case based on two different approaches for data gathering:

- Data gathering from dedicated R&D vehicle fleets deployed by an ADAS/AD company for ground truth (test dataset) as well as training dataset generation.
- Data gathering from regular autonomous vehicles for crowd-sourced training dataset generation.

4.1.2 High-level description of the use case

This use case relies on gathering new datasets from both dedicated R&D vehicles (sub-UC1.1) as well as from regular autonomous vehicles (sub-UC1.2) equipped with On-board Sensors such as Cameras and LIDARs. The collected data will first be processed locally by a software solution to detect any edge case (unusual, unlikely but possible situation), previously unseen events or driving situations that can lead to a deficient performance of an autonomous driving functionality. Then, the gathered data will be sent to the cloud through the MEC in order to train the Machine Learning model and to avoid any system failure. The new released updates are sent back from the cloud platform to the on-board development & testing system through the internet.

In UC1 sub-UC1.2 the objective is to improve the R&D cycle of AD/ADAS systems with a collaborative data gathering process based on crowdsourcing. This sub-use case is focused on using regular vehicles containing AD/ADAS functionalities as data sources instead of using dedicated vehicle fleets.

In this context, regular vehicle means a mass-market vehicle bought and driven by an end consumer.

Mass-market vehicles do not include ground truth generating sensors, which are very expensive, so in contrast with UC1.1, in UC1.2 the gathered data can only be used to expand the training dataset.

A background process streaming high-resolution raw sensor data could require most of the vehicle's 5G bandwidth, affecting the throughput and latency of safety-critical cooperative driving messaging therefore in UC1.2 the data sent by the vehicle is limited to lightweight processed sensor data, that could be the description of the detected objects/events, or some labelled images of for instance a new traffic sign detected.

4.1.3 Potential business models

This Use Case exploits vehicle data that is processed in three main domains: the vehicle itself, the MEC and the Cloud. Thus, the use case can be potentially exploited by a business actor that is focused on any of these domains.

For each domain, we can identify several products and several potential business models related to each of the products in the following table.

Table 3 Business models for Use Case 1 [31]

Domain	Product	Business model
Vehicle	Middleware for sensor synchronisation	License using recurring subscription or one-time payment.
	On-board software to identify and stream interesting new data chunks	License using recurring subscription, one-time payment or pay per use based on the transmitted data amount.
MEC	Software for data preparation	License using recurring subscription, one-time payment or pay per use based on the processed data amount.
	Software for MEC service registration, discovery and orchestration	License using recurring subscription or one-time payment.
Cloud	Software for new data reception and integration	License using recurring subscription, one-time payment or pay per use based on the processed data amount.
	Sensor data annotation tool	License using recurring subscription, one-time payment or pay per use based on the processed data amount.

4.1.4 Market opportunity

“The world’s most valuable resource is no longer oil, but data”⁴⁸. Data are also more versatile than any commodity on the planet because not all connections have been made yet; data fusion, analytics and novel-advanced models and algorithms can provide better or new insights. The process of connecting data sources to the burgeoning paradigms of Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning and Computer Vision systems has the potential to reduce the iterations and training loops and to boost Big Data systems.

“Using data” requires innovative thinking and cunning understanding of users’ needs and requirements.

- Sophisticated algorithms to prevent accidents may be integrated with the full traffic management infrastructure, enhancing the V2I collaboration. In fact, a growing need for new functions is expected. In this sense, the network will be the connectivity enabler and will increasingly move towards advanced value-added services. Therefore, we expect a growth in opportunities towards which future technological and architectural choices are also oriented. The moving vehicle will therefore be both a data generator to be sent / processed and a user of information from the environment.
- UC1 addresses the automotive industry need to generate comprehensive training and test datasets and it needs to create data management architectures that include instrumented vehicles equipped with ground-truth sensors and recording capabilities, large computation clusters to run Hardware-in-the-Loop (HiL) simulation tests, and Big Data solutions to orchestrate data transmission, archiving, analysis, and visualization.

Market opportunities may arise due to the several win-win situations for the different stakeholders that the UC1 addresses: drivers and passengers may get benefits from a faster update of AD/ADAS functionalities; automotive OEMs and suppliers may improve the research and development (R&D) process of the ML-based functionalities; big tech companies may potentially host the Cloud infrastructures; start-ups and innovative SMEs could offer innovative applications or services for data management and exploitation; telecoms could offer 5G connectivity and MEC resources in order to guarantee high performance in term of low latency, high throughput, secure connection. Furthermore, standards development organizations and policy makers would receive feedback from an innovative 5G use case that challenges 5G network resources and involves data privacy ethics.

4.1.5 Market barriers

The market opportunities that UC1 can exploit depend on collaborative models from both an architectural and a business point of view:

- From the business perspective, clear agreements between several actors have to be set up to facilitate the smooth data sharing process.
- Local regulations addressing citizens’ privacy may have a role when implementing such technologies.
- Building a network capable of providing continuity to the service will require a considerable investment.

Attention must be paid to developing a technical infrastructure that enables all stakeholders to build a virtuous system in which everyone can find their business for a more dynamic growth that otherwise would risk being developed in silo compartments and remain confined to a very limited use.

4.2 Use Case 2: Networking Parking

4.2.1 Use case motivation

⁴⁸ [The Economist](#)

This use case is based on data that can be transmitted from one vehicle to another (V2V) and/or to other RSUs (V2I) and eventually to third connected devices (V2X) to create different innovative services. 5G live messaging ensures the creation of value.

The 5G technology enables many connected devices per unit area, reaching a high density of devices (about 300.000 devices in a single cell) that can be connected to each other with the 5G key feature named Massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC). These devices transmit small amounts of traffic between each other. This characteristic enables a highly cooperative smart city, where it leverages a full location awareness to every road actor and promotes highly harmonized roads with lesser accidents and traffic.

Connected and autonomous driving create a safe and effective experience while providing comfort and convenience.

The Networking Parking use case offers accessibility and timesaving as its primary application's feature, as these are highly important concerns for today's consumers.

4.2.2 High-level description of the use case

This use case considers a rising start-up launching an innovative application called "Lazarus". One can download its client on a smartphone, while important and heavy computation will take place in the Lazarus system hosted in the Cloud. The 5GMETA MEC platform receives constantly sensors and devices data coming from both autonomous/connected vehicles (equipped with onboard cameras, sensors, and LIDARs) as well as road infrastructure. Then, the MEC makes the necessary processing (e.g., anonymization) to ensure privacy, security, and cleaning of the data and updates the 5GMETA Cloud platform with useful data only.

When given a trip's information, this application can accurately and dynamically determine the optimal departure time, the optimal route to get to the chosen destination in a target arrival time, and quickly find a free parking lot. These outputs are constantly updated whenever new events on the chosen path arise.

4.2.3 Potential business models

This Use Case exploits vehicle data that is processed in four main domains: the vehicle itself, the MEC, the Cloud and the roadside infrastructure. Thus, the use case can be potentially exploited by a business actor that is focused on any of these domains. For each domain, we can identify several products and potential related business models as shown in Table 4.

Table 4 Business models for Use Case 2 [31]

Domain	Product	Business model
Cloud	Lazarus Server	License using recurring subscription or price per computed itinerary. (paid by Lazarus application user)
Vehicle	Vehicle data sent to MEC	Data consumption paid by Lazarus server (based on data usage)
Roadside infrastructure	RSU data sent to MEC	Data consumption paid by Lazarus server (based on data usage)
MEC	Video and sensor data analysis	Server and side cost paid by Lazarus server

4.2.4 Market opportunity

All of us are accustomed to a widespread use of supports to be guided to a predetermined destination with our car or a car sharing service. The need to travel combined with the need to reduce travel time, or at least be able to predict it, make us appreciate more and more the features available on our favourite navigation system. In this context, therefore, a network that provides increasingly precise information

on the state of traffic and the availability of parking spaces upon our arrival is an element that will be of strategic importance to respond to the demanding expectations of the market and to guarantee a reduction on environmental impacts.

An intelligent network capable of connecting vehicles and people to an intelligent Mobility-as-a-service could provide users with the ability to choose the best transport means according to their needs to reach a place paying the right “ticket”. The network could be used to collect information and offer value-added services to several subjects who could collaborate to offer to the final user a series of possible transport choices that he/she can access.

- The system in UC2 is focusing on “collaborative parking”: the “collaborative” and “networking” concept, based on the communication between the platform, the app and multiple users that are moving may be exploited also for different purposes, not strictly related to parking. For instance, the feature can be integrated with systems providing, e.g., booking of restaurants or other services (including public services).
- The event industry is increasingly focusing on the reduction of its impact. The system developed through UC2 can be exploited by collaborating with organizers of big events. For instance, in the context of a big festival, festival goers may have to download the app to enter the festival. In this case, they could use the same app to create “groups” to reach the festival through a shared service.
- Local administrations will certainly be interested in encouraging and financing the adoption of systems for a more informed use of vehicles and alleviate traffic congestion in urban centres.
- End users can think of subscribing to services to reserve parking spaces according to their needs and use.

4.2.5 Market barriers

To be effective the UC2 technology requires a collaborative model from both an architectural and a business point of view. Attention must be paid to developing a system that allows all stakeholders being able to build a virtuous system in which everyone can find their business for a more dynamic growth also having the ability to integrate and collaborate with current services that are already widely used by end users.

- From the business perspective, clear agreements between several actors have to be set up to facilitate the smooth data sharing process.
- Local regulations addressing citizens’ privacy may have a role when implementing such technologies.
- To encourage the use of this service, citizens must have a considerable offer of parking spaces that can be managed by the service.

4.3 Use case 3: Driving Safety & Awareness

4.3.1 Use case motivation

The main motivation for developing this use case is road safety, aiming to tackle a specific/edge case which is Driving Misbehaviour. The use case foresees two scenarios:

1. The driver is disengaged or no longer fit to drive due to an unknown reason reducing her/his physical capacity, and with a potentially engaged vital prognosis, therefore it is possible to speak about “Health-related Misbehaviour” and the emphasis should be made on but not limited to “Increasing the Driving Safety” to prevent road fatalities and crashes.
2. The driver is physically able to drive, but she/he misjudges/misunderstands road network & signs which leads to a Driving Misbehaviour like for instance “Wrong-Way Driving”. While the

primary focus here should be on “Increasing the Driving Awareness” to alert surrounding vehicles, it should not be limited to only that.

4.3.2 High-level description of the use case

This use case deals with driving Misbehaviour Detection (MBD) and Misbehaviour Response (MBR) which has two objectives: increase driving safety by preventing road fatalities and crashes involving the currently misbehaving vehicle, and increase the awareness of surrounding vehicles by alerting them about the existence of this potential threat to road safety. Among all possible driving misbehavior situations, this use case tackles two specific scenarios: the first is Health-related Misbehaviour (sub-UC3.1) where the driver is no longer able to drive the vehicle due to an unknown reason reducing her/his physical capacity, and with a potentially engaged vital prognosis. The second is Driving Misbehaviour (sub-UC3.2) where the driver is physically able to drive, but she/he misinterprets road network & signs. This use case relies on two Traffic Management Center (TMC) high level services: MBD and MBR that will be hosted by the 5GMETA Platform. In both scenarios, the MBD is continuously sensing the vehicle’s motion to detect potential driving misbehavior. When misbehavior is detected by the vehicle, MBD notifies the MBR service which will provide the appropriate response and will alert surrounding vehicles about the existence of a misbehaving vehicle in the area. The MBR service then requests the remote control of the vehicle.

4.3.3 Potential business models

This Use Case exploits vehicle data that is processed in three main domains: the vehicle itself, the MEC and the Cloud. Given the primary focus of this UC (Road Safety & Awareness), in most cases a “Public-utility charging rules” strategy should be promoted for data consumption, and to ensure large/massive adoption by End User’s. This could be achieved based on a cost-free pricing, or a reduced one, indirectly sustained by customers that buy vehicles equipped with such products or during vehicle registration, as well by other actors through mutual agreements.

Table 5 Business models for Use Case 3 [31]

Domain	Service/Product	Business model
Vehicle	Driver Monitoring System (DMS)	License included with the vehicle services & equipment or one-time payment.
	ToD-Capable L3/L4 AD System	License included with the vehicle services & equipment or one-time payment.
	ETSI Basic Services (CAM, DENM, etc.) as Misbehaviour Response (MBR) service	Two type of business models: V2V communication through PC5 and non-licenced bands: free or one-time payment. V2I/V2N through Uu and licenced bands: License using recurring subscription or one-time payment.
MEC	Misbehaviour Detection (MBD) service	License using recurring subscription or one-time payment.
	Tele-Operated Driving (ToD) as Misbehaviour Response (MBR) service	License using recurring subscription, one-time payment or pay per use based on the processed data amount & category.
	ETSI Basic Services (CAM, DENM, etc.) as Misbehaviour Response (MBR) service	License using recurring subscription or one-time payment.

Domain	Service/Product	Business model
Cloud	Software for Misbehaviour Detection (MSB) service	License using recurring subscription or one-time payment.
	ETSI Basic Services (CAM, DENM, etc.) as Misbehaviour Response (MBR) service	License using recurring subscription or one-time payment.

4.3.4 Market opportunity

Ensuring Driving Safety & Awareness, by properly detecting and mitigating driving misbehaviour situations, could be the evolution of an intelligent network into a “caring network”. Of course, the complexity to detect misbehaviour situations will need development and effort from all involved stakeholders to cooperate and to rely on multiple data sources, which leads to a large volume of data to be transferred in a reliable fashion, before being timely processed. This Use Case is very challenging, but it could open new business opportunities for different actors who could provide these services to both public institutions and private companies: the end customer would undoubtedly be very attracted to this type of service which would guarantee benefits that perhaps today we are not yet able to quantify.

The system developed in this UC may have tangible opportunities into the market, for instance:

- The interoperable EU-wide eCall number 112 automatically dials Europe's single emergency number 112 in the event of a serious road accident and communicates the vehicle's location to the emergency services. It may be interesting to create a linkage with such eCall European infrastructure by allowing the communication between the 5GMETA platform and the eCall numbers.
- Smart wearable devices are widely spread for today's active lifestyle and health monitoring: anyone (including vulnerable users) has the opportunity to have his/her body status continuously monitored and – in some cases, connected to the public-health systems. The system developed in sub-UC3.1 allows vehicles of vulnerable users to have a real time detection and response such that both in case of health issues causing misbehaviour, there is a prompt reaction in terms of rescue of the ill driver. New market opportunities may arise by partnering with producers of such (wearable) devices (e.g., smartphone apps, smartwatches, fitbands, etc.) and – at the same time – allow for a more detailed screening of the drivers' body. Furthermore, such system, developed in sub-UC3.1, may be integrated not only in “normal” cars, but also in other connected vehicles used by impaired people, allowing for potential partnerships with producers of such type of vehicles.
- The system developed in sub-UC3.2 collects important data related to incidents due to wrong drivers' decisions, allowing to understand which road areas (e.g., signals, crossroads, traffic lights, etc.) create confusion to drivers or may be dangerous in case of drivers' distractions. Transport planners may use this data to upgrade or update the road infrastructure and – hopefully - avoid future incidents. In terms of market opportunity, public-private partnerships may be activated allowing, for instance, for public incentives addressed to drivers deciding to integrate the system in their vehicles.
- Another potential market opportunity which is not considered in the 1st version of UC3 but could be considered in future releases is the possibility to have “Predictive QoS” as a 5G enabler. Although this one is a simple enabler, building this information requires different type of data: Meteorological, Road Occupancy, Network usage (so by fusing all this data, you can predict ahead what will be the quality of your network, and provide this information to the Road Operator that is conducting the Teleoperated Driving (ToD)). If it is not safe to do the ToD due to any reason, it relies on another solution (ADAS) or just stops the vehicle.

- The huge data collected will allow building analytics that can be proposed to different markets.
- The ability to do predictive analytics can provide various commercial categories to be able to offer products such as a tire change, oil change and in general all the components that need cyclical maintenance.

End users can subscribe to alerting services based on the maintenance necessary to avoid breakdowns and inefficiency.

4.3.5 Market barriers

Also, in this UC the complexity of the service will require the involvement of many actors and therefore it will be important to find a business model where everyone can have their own advantage to be able to correctly support a very important development.

- In terms of cybersecurity, concerns may be raised on the decision of what should be the right procedure for taking control of the vehicle. The involved technology allows for a Secure Procedure for Remote Control of Vehicle in both sub-UCs. Indeed, the procedure has to be secure otherwise it may face resistance from end-users.
- Tele Operated Driving (ToD) used for Misbehaviour Response could raise ethical questions that we should handle, for instance: ToD could be considered as an intrusive solution? ToD could face resistance from end-users, reducing its acceptance? What kind of response should we provide in the case of a “Wrong Way Driving”?

5 STAKEHOLDERS' ANALYSIS

This stakeholders' analysis has been divided into four steps, which lead to the identification and categorization of all potential stakeholders of the 5GMETA platform. Those steps are based on the writers' subjective definition of level of comparison, categorization and on value rating. The first two steps are described here below, concluding this analysis with an overview of the stakeholders by means of an interest vs. power matrix technique. Each value and level will be revised in the second version of this deliverable, and validated or updated based on inputs coming from real stakeholders' assessment. The last two steps are described here, but the analysis will be yield in the second version of this deliverable.

The following stepwise approach has been followed to list stakeholders for the 5GMETA business.

Step 1: Identify the stakeholders: A brainstorm on the stakeholders that seem relevant in the context of 5GMETA has been done in 5GMETA. Also, a list of relevant people, companies, organisations affected by the 5GMETA developments and who have a vested interest in its success or failure has been produced. Based on that a first draft of a classification of these stakeholders has been done to understand their role in the market.

Step 2: Prioritize the stakeholders: An assessment of the stakeholders' level of influence and interest has been done, resulting in an interest vs power matrix. This assessment is based on the following questions to derive the power and influence of stakeholders mainly from their place in the value chain:

1. What do stakeholders expect from the project and how do they benefit?
2. Are there any conflicting interests that the stakeholder may have with respect to the project?
3. How committed is the stakeholder to the project? Is he/she willing to commit tangible resources?
4. Are there relationship conflicts between stakeholders that can hinder the project?

Step 3: Perform a Market intelligence about these Stakeholders: This step will detail the insights on the stakeholders identified by means of the interest vs. power matrix as the ones with high power and high interest on the 5GMETA project. This detailed insight will help 5GMETA to define marketing communication and dissemination actions towards these stakeholders and to develop the right business development activities. Once the stakeholders are prioritized and their attitude towards the project is assessed, and more insight on the top stakeholders has been generated, a marketing communication plan will be created to have an adequate stakeholder engagement with 5GMETA.

Step 4: Creating a Marketing Communication Plan: As this deliverable is a desktop research, it will also identify suggestions for active market research to conclude and complete the obtained insights in a next version of this deliverable. The results and insights generated by the marketing communication plan will be the main source for updating the deliverable.

5.1 Step 1: Identify the 5GMETA stakeholders

The list of stakeholders can be gathered out of various sources, such as:

- As a recap, the already listed stakeholders (players) listed in the other deliverables of the 5GMETA project;
- Listed stakeholders out of SENSORIS ERTICO innovation platform;
- Stakeholders related to particular use cases.

Extract from 'D2.2 5GMETA use cases and their requirements'

Deliverable D2.2 “5GMETA use cases and their requirements” [31] publishes a thorough analysis and description of these stakeholders. The most interesting findings are listed below.

- Drivers and passengers are the final end-users of the applications, products, and services, making use of the 5GMETA environment. They will not directly use the system itself, but they will use and buy the applications products and services based upon the 5GMETA system. They are important stakeholders as they decide to buy the final product/service/application as a stakeholder at the end of the value chain, but of course they are not an immediate customer for the 5GMETA platform services themselves.
- Automotive OEMs and suppliers need to implement the sensors in their vehicles. An alternative might be that the drivers and passengers are using OBU (on board units) or their mobile phones to replace the in-vehicle equipment. OEMS can also be end users of the 5GMETA environment, using the applications, products and services from service providers that have enriched the 5GMETA raw outputs towards valid offerings for the automation of the car. As automation moves on in the market, they will become the final indirect end-user of the 5GMETA system.
- Road infrastructure operators are important stakeholders as they can use the 5GMETA services for improving use cases like the ones mentioned in this document with their own added value services and guidance to the drivers/ or automated vehicles.
- Big tech companies (GAFA+) are stakeholders because they operate the Cloud environment and provide the IT infrastructure for performing AI and big data analysis. They can also act as (indirect) competitors.
- Start-ups and innovative SMEs are expected to generate new ideas and business models with the 5GMETA environment.
- Service providers. They are essential stakeholders because they enrich the 5GMETA environment and transform its raw outputs to valid services for end users.
- Mobility providers: these are all types of operators of vehicles, like bus companies, etc. In this respect, they can act as final ‘indirect’ end users of the 5GMETA system. But they will be influenced by the drivers of their fleet, accepting, or influencing the purchase of services.
- Connectivity providers are an essential supplier to link the 5GMETA MEC with the cloud on the 5G network.
- Insurance companies can make use of 5GMETA environment to determine advanced and smart insurance offerings to end users.
- Telematics companies Can provide services and OBU (on board units) based upon 5GMETA.
- Retail operators: This terminology has to be interpreted in the broadest sense. It includes all organisations that create an active sales activity towards end users.
- Standards development organisations can play an influencing role as a stakeholder, as the 5GMETA system will need to interact with many other environments where the interfaces are subject to standards. E.g., related to coming CCAM standards, or interact with digital twin related standards like DATEX II and TN-ITS and public transport data sharing standards.
- Policy makers can look at the new opportunities for services, products and applications, made possible by the 5GMETA environment and can decide to take these as an input for e.g., new type of

regulations on e.g., safety applications, and transport automation. As the data and services from 5GMETA can play an important role in enhancing these type of use cases, policy makers can demand a tighter ‘compliance ‘scheme for the 5GMETA.

- The recruitment of additional stakeholders will take place continuously after the initial phase through project activities, with project partners and external projects interactions as well as dissemination initiatives.

Stakeholders identified from the SENSORIS ERTICO innovation network

SENSORIS⁴⁹ is an ERTICO innovation platform dealing with the sharing of sensor data in the cloud. This platform is a membership organisation, consisting of relevant stakeholders that try to establish a (de-facto) standard for this type of functionality.

The stakeholders involved are mentioned below:

- ADAS Manufacturers. These companies provide sensors, products, applications, and services to assist drivers in driving and parking functions by means of a safe human-machine interface. Many of these products and services are integrated into the vehicle.
- Location and content service providers: these companies provide digital maps or related services, applications, and products.
- Navigation systems suppliers: These companies provide complex systems, making use of the digital map technology, like L3 & L4 automation services, LIDAR based navigations, eHorizon applications.
- Telco and cloud infrastructure providers. These companies provide the connectivity or the supporting cloud big data systems including big data analysis tools.
- Vehicle manufacturers. They provide the vehicles integrating the ADAS systems, making use of the digital maps and innovative navigation systems.
- Other companies like academia and technology consulting companies.

Stakeholders identified in relation to the 5GMETA Use Cases

Within 5GMETA, 3 use cases are withheld to be fully worked out and demonstrated in live environments, as described in Section 3. The identified stakeholders are reported in Table 6.

Table 6 Use Cases Stakeholders

Use case 1: R&D Live Training Loop	Use Case 2: Networking Parking	Use case 3: Driving Safety & Awareness
Academia	Public parking operators	ADAS suppliers
Developers	Private parking operators	OEMS
R&D companies developing applications, products and services	Real estate companies	Public authorities/policy makers
Automotive OEMs and car manufacturers	Private parking in buildings	Traffic management infrastructure and services suppliers

⁴⁹ [SENSORIS](#)

Use case 1: R&D Live Training Loop	Use Case 2: Networking Parking	Use case 3: Driving Safety & Awareness
	Private parking in companies	Traffic Safety associations
		Drivers and passengers
		Automotive OEMS and suppliers

5.2 Step 2: Prioritize the stakeholders

1. What do stakeholders expect from the project and how do they benefit?

This step focuses on defining the interest level of the identified stakeholders. Thus, the analysis of the stakeholders' expectations and their benefits from the project has to be done. As a reference, the 5GMETA products, services and applications identified in the three use cases will be used. The analysis is a first order empiric analysis on how the stakeholders can show interest in these products. The following code will be applied to quantify the stakeholder interest:

- 0:** No envisioned interest
- 1:** Some interest expected
- 2:** High interest expected

This analysis is a personal subjective assessment by the authors. The outcome of this analysis leads to a hypothesis that needs to be validated by active market research to the targeted stakeholders in step 3 of the stakeholder analysis. This will be addressed in step 4: 'The marketing communication plan'.

This explains why a certain score given is not elaborated in this document but can be part of a bigger discussion in a workshop with the 5GMETA project partners, as well as other future events such as hackathons, as Task 6.3 is currently organizing and will do in the next months. So far, the score is the subjective score by the authors. After the results we can analyse mathematically the impact if the subjective score would not fit the general opinion of the project partners.

The product categories that were identified by the use cases are grouped by vehicle, MEC and Cloud related 5GMETA product services and applications ideas.

Vehicle-related products and services

The categories considered for the vehicle products, referred to the three use cases, are:

- R&D Live Training Loop
 - Middleware for sensor Synchronization
 - On-Board software to identify and stream interesting new data chunks
- Networking parking
 - Vehicle data sent to MEC
- Driving safety and awareness
 - DMS Driver Monitoring System
 - ToD-Capable L3/L4 System
 - ETSI Basic Services (CAM, DENM, etc.) as Misbehaviour Response (MBR) service.

Table 7 predicts the interest of stakeholders to vehicle related 5GMETA products. For a better data visualization, this prediction of interest is reported also in Figure 3 as a bar chart.

Table 7 Stakeholders' interest related to vehicle 5GMETA products

	R&D Live Training Loop		Networking parking	Driving safety and awareness			TOTAL
	Middleware	On-Board software	Vehicle data	DMS	ToD-Capable L3/L4 System	ETSI Basic services as MBR	
Drivers and passengers	0	1	0	2	2	2	7
Automotive OEMs and suppliers	2	2	1	2	2	1	10
Road infrastructure operators	0	1	2	2	2	2	9
Tech companies	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
Start-Ups/innovators	1	1	2	1	1	1	7
Service providers	2	2	2	2	2	2	12
Mobility providers	1	1	1	2	2	2	9
Connectivity providers	1	1	1	1	1	1	6
Insurance companies	0	0	1	2	2	2	7
Telematics companies	1	2	2	1	1	1	8
Standards development organisations	0	0	1	0	1	1	3
Policy makers	0	0	1	1	1	1	4
ADAS manufacturers	2	2	1	2	2	2	11
Location and content providers	1	2	1	1	1	1	7
Navigation system suppliers	2	2	2	1	2	1	10
Public parking operators	0	0	2	2	2	2	8
Private parking operators	0	0	2	2	2	2	8
Real estate companies	0	0	1	0	1	0	2
Private parking in buildings	0	0	1	0	1	0	2
Private parking @ companies	0	0	1	0	1	0	2
Traffic management service providers	0	0	2	1	2	1	6
Traffic safety associations	0	0	1	1	1	2	5
TOTAL	13	17	29	26	32	27	

Figure 3 Stakeholders' interest related to vehicle 5GMETA products

Automotive OEMs, Service providers, ADAS manufacturers and Navigation system providers are assumed to have the biggest interest here. The insight which vehicle related 5GMETA product will generate the highest interest from the stakeholders can be also derived, which is the 'L3 and L4 automation products for driving safety and giving awareness to drivers', and the 'vehicle data sent to MEC for automated parking purposes' (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Vehicle related Products with the highest stakeholder interest

MEC-related products and services

The same analysis has been carried out for the MEC related 5GMETA products. In this case, the analysed categories have been defined as follow:

- R&D Live Training Loop
 - Software for data preparation
- Networking parking
 - Video and sensor data analysis
- Driving safety and awareness
 - Misbehaviour Detection (MBD) service
 - Vehicle Digital Twin
 - Tele-Operated Driving (ToD) as Misbehaviour Response (MBR) service
 - ETSI Basic Services (CAM, DENM, etc.) as Misbehaviour Response (MBR) service

Table 8 Stakeholders' interest related to MEC 5GMETA products

	R&D Live Training Loop	Networking parking	Driving safety and awareness				TOTAL
	Software for data preparation	Video and sensor data analysis	MBD service	Vehicle Digital Twin	ToD as MBR	ETSI Basic Service as MBR	
Drivers and passengers	0	1	2	0	1	2	6
Automotive OEMs and suppliers	2	2	2	2	2	2	12
Road infrastructure operators	1	1	2	2	2	2	10
Tech companies	1	1	1	1	1	1	6
Start-Ups/innovators	1	1	1	1	1	1	6
Service providers	2	2	2	1	2	2	11
Mobility providers	0	1	2	1	1	2	7
Connectivity providers	1	1	1	1	1	1	6
Insurance companies	0	2	2	0	1	2	7
Telematics companies	2	2	2	2	2	2	12
Standards development organisations	0	0	0	2	1	1	4
Policy makers	0	0	1	1	1	2	5
ADAS manufacturers	2	2	2	2	2	2	12
Location and content providers	2	1	1	2	2	1	9
Navigation system suppliers	2	1	1	2	1	2	9
Public parking operators	0	0	2	1	2	2	7
Private parking operators	0	0	2	1	2	2	7
Real estate companies	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Private parking in buildings	0	0	2	1	2	2	7
Private parking @ companies	0	0	2	1	2	2	7
Traffic management service providers	0	0	1	2	2	2	7
Traffic safety associations	0	1	2	1	1	2	7
TOTAL	16	19	33	27	32	38	

The information in the previous table is depicted in graph format below.

Figure 5 Stakeholders' interest related to MEC 5GMETA products

This analysis reveals again Automotive OEMs, Service providers and ADAS system manufacturers as the stakeholders with the highest relative interest.

For this segment, apparently also Telematics service providers can show a lot of potential.

The MEC product that gets the highest relative interest from stakeholders is predicted as the *ETSI Basic Services (CAM, DENM, etc.) as Misbehaviour Response (MBR) service* for enhancing driving safety and giving enhanced awareness to drivers (as reported in Figure 6).

Figure 6 5GMETA MEC products interests from stakeholders

Cloud-related products and services

Finally, for the 5GMETA Cloud services the categories considered are:

- R&D Live Training Loop
 - Software for MEC service registration, discovery and orchestration
 - Software for new data reception and integration
 - Sensor data annotation tool
- Networking parking
 - Lazarus Server
- Driving safety and awareness
 - Software for Misbehaviour Detection (MBD) service
 - Vehicle Digital Twin
 - ETSI Basic Services (CAM, DENM, etc.) as Misbehaviour Response (MBR) service

Table 9 Stakeholders' interest related to CLOUD 5GMETA products

	R&D Live Training Loop			Networking parking	Driving safety and awareness			TOTAL
	Software for MEC services	Software for data reception and integration	Sensor data annotation tool	Vehicle Digital Twin	Software for MBD	Vehicle Digital Twin	ETSI Basic Service as MBR	
Drivers and passengers	0	0	0	2	2	1	1	6
Automotive OEMs and suppliers	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	8
Road infrastructure operators	0	1	1	0	2	2	2	8
Tech companies	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	8
Start-Ups/innovators	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	7
Service providers	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	13
Mobility providers	0	0	0	1	2	2	2	7
Connectivity providers	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
Insurance companies	0	0	0	1	2	2	2	7
Telematics companies	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	12
Standards development organisations	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	3
Policy makers	0	0	0	1	1	2	1	5
ADAS manufacturers	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	14

Location and content providers	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	3
Navigation system suppliers	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	3
Public parking operators	1	1	0	2	2	2	1	9
Private parking operators	1	1	0	2	2	2	1	9
Real estate companies	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	2
Private parking in buildings	1	1	0	2	2	2	1	9
Private parking @ companies	1	1	0	2	2	2	1	9
Traffic management service providers	0	0	0	2	1	2	1	6
Traffic safety associations	0	0	0	1	2	2	2	7
TOTAL	14	16	9	31	29	33	24	

The information in the previous table is depicted in bar chart format below (Figure 7).

Figure 7 Stakeholders' interest related to CLOUD 5GMETA products

This analysis shows again the high relative interest of service providers and ADAS providers. Interest from telematics providers can also be noticed.

The cloud 5GMETA products with the highest interest is predicted by Figure 8 as the driving safer and generating more driver awareness products, as well as the Lazarus automated parking server idea.

Figure 8 5GMETA CLOUD products interests from stakeholders

In order to come to a conclusion, it is necessary to determine the weighting factors of the interest domains vehicle, MEC and cloud. For the time being we assume that the three interest domains have the same weight. This allows us to just sum all results to get the combined interest of the 5GMETA stakeholders.

Overall interest in 5GMETA products and services

The overall results are shown in the next bar chart (Figure 9).

Figure 9 Total relative interest of stakeholders in the 5GMETA products/project

ADAS, Service and Telematics providers show the highest interests in the 5GMETA products.

2. Are there any conflicting interests that the stakeholder may have with the project?

Potential conflicts from the previously considered stakeholders are reported below, describing the stakeholders that might have conflicts and the reasons why.

- Automotive OEMs and suppliers: OEMs deploy the 'neutral server concept', that can be seen as a competitive approach to the 5GMETA infrastructure. and they gather in SENSORIS to set a de facto standard for sensor data sharing.
- Road infrastructure operators: Road infrastructure operators have a strong buying power by their obligation to issue public tenders, and look for level playing fields, avoiding vendor lock in. It can be difficult for 5GMETA to enter their market.
- Tech companies: Tech companies can decide to build a competitive infrastructure.
- Start-Ups/innovators: Potentially, some start-ups want to develop such a 5GMETA infrastructure themselves, as a competitive approach. The services provided by 5GMETA may not completely fill in their needs for realising the innovations.
- Telematics companies: Telematics companies can decide to develop a competitive and closed environment.
- Policy makers: It can be unclear for policy makers what role they need to play and how to regulate the several new possible services that can come out of 5GMETA.

3. How committed is the stakeholder to the project? Are they willing to commit tangible resources?

For this analysis we use a score 1 to 5, where 5 represents the highest score. Obtained results are reported in Figure 10.

Figure 10 Potential project 5GMETA engagement score

From the engagement score analysis, it shows up that there are good possibilities to commit tangible resources mostly from stakeholders related to traffic management services, ADAS manufacturers, parking operators (private less than public), and service providers. This analysis cuts out a wide range of potential stakeholders, and thus a validation process will verify the goodness of those assumptions and how many of those stakeholders might gain a higher score.

4. Are there relationship conflicts between stakeholders that can hinder the project?

The following list reports, for each stakeholder, the total number of possible conflicts and with which other stakeholder they might have them:

- Drivers and passengers' number of potential conflicts: 0
- Automotive OEMS and suppliers' number of potential conflicts: 7
 1. Road infrastructure operators
 2. Service providers
 3. Mobility providers
 4. Telematics companies
 5. Policy makers
 6. Traffic management service providers
 7. Traffic safety associations
- Road infrastructure operators' number of potential conflicts: 7
 1. Connectivity providers
 2. Telematics companies
 3. Policy makers
 4. Public parking operators
 5. Private parking operators
 6. Private parking in buildings
 7. Private parking @ companies
- Tech companies' number of potential conflicts: 2
 1. Service providers
 2. Telematics companies
- Start-Ups/innovators' number of potential conflicts: 7
 1. Service providers
 2. Mobility providers
 3. Telematics companies
 4. Policy makers
 5. ADAS manufacturers
 6. Private parking operators
 7. Traffic management service providers
- Service providers' number of potential conflicts: 7
 1. Telematics companies
 2. Standards development organisations
 3. Policy makers
 4. ADAS manufacturers
 5. Location and content providers
 6. Navigation system suppliers
 7. Traffic management service providers

- Mobility providers' number of potential conflicts: 1
 1. Policy makers
- Connectivity providers' number of potential conflicts: 7
 1. Standards development organisations
 2. Policy makers
 3. Public parking operators
 4. Private parking operators
 5. Real estate companies
 6. Private parking in buildings
 7. Private parking @ companies
- Insurance companies' number of potential conflicts: 1
 1. Traffic safety associations
- Telematics companies' number of potential conflicts: 3
 1. Location and content providers
 2. Navigation system suppliers
 3. Traffic management service providers
- Standards development organisations' number of potential conflicts: 0
- Policy makers' number of potential conflicts: 4
 1. Private parking operators
 2. Real estate companies
 3. Private parking in buildings
 4. Private parking @ companies
- ADAS manufacturers' number of potential conflicts: 0
- Location and content providers' number of potential conflicts: 0
- Navigation system suppliers' number of potential conflicts: 0
- Public parking operators' number of potential conflicts: 4
 1. Private parking operators
 2. Real estate companies
 3. Private parking in buildings
 4. Private parking @ companies
- Private parking operators' number of potential conflicts: 1
 1. Real estate companies
- Real estate companies' number of potential conflicts: 0
- Private parking in buildings' number of potential conflicts: 0
- Private parking @ companies' number of potential conflicts: 0
- Traffic management service providers' number of potential conflicts: 0
- Traffic safety associations' number of potential conflicts: 0

5.2.1 Stakeholders' mapping

Stakeholder mapping is a process that identifies all the stakeholders in the organization or the project and assigns priority to the ones which are more involved in the project. The mapping is essential from a strategic perspective as some stakeholders have more influence on the project than others and they can drive the project to the ground if not handled correctly.

Stakeholders have been prioritized by assessing their level of influence and level of interest. This has led to the power-interest matrix. This technique divides the stakeholders mentioned in the previous section into four parts and allocates them on a map. The position, allocated to a stakeholder on the map, shows the level of interest and power that each stakeholder has and the actions that 5GMETA needs to take with them. The categories are [29] the following:

High power, highly interested people: Manage Closely. These are key stakeholders with high power and high interest in the project with the largest impact on the success of the project. The expectations of these stakeholders need to be met and establishing a close working relationship with them is beneficial. 5GMETA must fully engage these people and make the greatest efforts to satisfy them.

High power, less interested people: Keep Satisfied. These are the stakeholders which have high power in the project but low interest. They can influence the overall context of the project but are not completely interested in the outcome. The power they yield should be managed with caution as they can also impact the project in a negative way. 5GMETA should keep these stakeholders satisfied, but at a moderate level.

Low power, highly interested people: Keep Informed. These stakeholders do not have a lot of power but have high interest in the project. They are helpful during the construction phase of the project and can assist in tackling of issues, use cases that are needed, additional implementations, etc. They need to be kept informed about the project and can also be used for testing purposes. 5GMETA should adequately inform these stakeholders since these stakeholders are categorized as 'advisors' to the project.

Low power, less interested people: Monitor with minimum effort. These stakeholders will eventually benefit from the project but will not play any role in the decision-making process. They are not much relevant regarding the success of the project, so it is better to keep the communication limited with them. 5GMETA might keep in contact and observe if they are moving to other parts of the map.

To come to the final score of stakeholder's interests in 5GMETA, a final score on Stakeholder' analysis has been determined. To achieve this, all results have been combined and normalised to a maximum score of 5 to allow the stakeholder positioning on the power/interest matrix.

The following subjective formula considers the influence considering the previous analysis. The weighting factors proposed are:

- Factor a: 30% (or 3 points out of 10) for a relevant positive engagement of the stakeholder in the project.
- Factor b: -20% (or minus 2 points) for a negative interest because the stakeholder sees itself in a relevant potential conflict with the project deliverables.
- Factor c: -10% (or minus 1 point) if the stakeholder shows relevant potential conflicts with other stakeholders.

The word 'relevance' is related to observing a significant impact created by this stakeholder, average to the other stakeholders. All values higher than 3 will result in positioning those stakeholders in the right half of the power/interest matrix (High power, highly interested people: Manage Closely).

To lead to the definition of the power/influence level, relevant business categories that stakeholders can be grouped to, defined by a generic value chain, have been drafted. Indeed, a value system, or an

industry value chain⁵⁰, includes the suppliers that provide the inputs necessary to the firm along with their value chains. After the firm creates products, these products pass through the value chains of distributors (which also have their own value chains), all the way to the customers. All parts of these chains are included in the value system. The generic value chain is reported in Figure 11.

Figure 11 Generic Stakeholder value chain

It is a common understanding that the stakeholders that belong to the business categories (more to the right in Figure 11: End users, Retail distribution) are the stakeholders that add the most value to the project's business, even though they might not be the most profitable ones. From a power/influence perspective, value chain categories from Figure 11 have been used to analyse, for each stakeholder, to which category they belong to.

The following subjective analysis was made by the authors giving the following ranks:

- 1: For suppliers
- 2: For Manufacturers, Assembly, and software
- 3: For integrator/service providers
- 4: For retail distribution
- 5: For end users

Rank 2 is important since 5GMETA products, services and applications are created by project partners, as manufacturers, assembly, and software activities. Therefore, rank 2 stakeholders are also immediately recognised as being 'competitors'. Table 10 gives an overview of the ranking results.

Table 10 Rank in the value chain (power)

1	2	3	4	5
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tech companies • Location and content providers • Navigation system suppliers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Telematics companies • ADAS manufacturers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automotive OEMs and suppliers • Start-Ups/innovators • Service providers • Standards development organisations • Traffic management service providers • Traffic safety associations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobility providers • Connectivity providers • Insurance companies • Public parking operators • Private parking operators • Real estate companies • Private parking in buildings • Private parking @ companies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drivers and passengers

⁵⁰ [Value chain, Wikipedia](#)

From both analyses, it is now possible to derive the power/interest matrix. Therefore, both results have been normalized to the same values in a proposed rank 1-5 where the axis of the power/interest matrix lay on value 3 in both axes. The result on the power/interest matrix is shown in Figure 12, while scores of each stakeholder are reported in Table 11.

Table 11 Stakeholders interest and power scores

Stakeholder	Interest	Power
Drivers and passengers	1,9	5
Automotive OEMS and suppliers	3,0	3
Road infrastructure operators	2,5	5
Tech companies	1,5	1
Start-Ups/innovators	1,8	3
Service providers	3,7	3
Mobility providers	2,7	4
Connectivity providers	1,3	4
Insurance companies	2,8	4
Telematics companies	3,1	2
Standards development organisations	1,8	3
Policy makers	1,1	5
ADAS manufacturers	5,0	2
Location and content providers	2,2	1
Navigation system suppliers	2,5	1
Public parking operators	3,5	4
Private parking operators	3,3	4
Real estate companies	0,4	4
Private parking in buildings	1,8	4
Private parking @ companies	1,8	4
Traffic management service providers	3,1	3
Traffic safety associations	3,0	3

Figure 12 5GMETA Power vs Interest matrix

The most distinctive stakeholders in Figure 12 matrix have been identified. Of course, the decision lines that form the matrix are subjective choices.

Looking to these results, it is important to look at other candidates to enter the upper right quadrant of the matrix, such as 'OEMS & suppliers' and 'Traffic safety organisations' (both coordinates 3,3 in the above table).

This graph will be interpreted as the basis of a hypothesis that needs to be confirmed by active market research in step 4, which will be available in the next deliverable version.

6 CONNECTION WITH 5GMETA'S TECHNICAL WORK

The objective of this deliverable is mainly to understand which new business models can be built on top of the 5GMETA platform. For this reason, the connection with the technical work is mainly related to WP2: 5G Functions design & use cases.

The deliverable D2.1: “5G requirements & standards” describes the main 5G features and the relevant standards that lay the foundation of the 5GMETA project work. This deliverable has been used as starting point for the market analysis because it describes the general context where the 5GMETA platform will work.

The general use cases connected to 5GMETA have been analysed in D2.2 “5GMETA use cases and their requirements”, together with the use cases that will be implemented and validated in the different PSs. These general use case categories have been the input for the section on Market Intelligence where an initial market analysis of the three main use cases has been performed. This will be extended in the second issue of D6.1 and completed with the results coming from the Hackathons and from other activities in WP6.

Finally, the deliverable D2.3: “Initial definition of the 5GMETA platform”, has been the input for the competitors' analysis: here the main competitors of the 5GMETA platform have been identified starting from the initial definition of how the platform will work and which features will be implemented. This study will be further extended and will try to highlight the points of strength of the 5GMETA solution with respect to the other platform already in the market (also considering new ones). The result of WP3 (not yet available for this issue of D6.1) and the final definition of the architecture will close the definition of the platform's features and capabilities and allow the finalization of the competitor's analysis.

7 CONCLUSION

This deliverable contains the first release of Market Research and Stakeholder analysis for the 5GMETA project, which allowed us to have a better perspective of where the 5GMETA platform can play its role in the market and which are the main stakeholders to monitor closely.

The market analysis shows a broad study of the key trends in the automotive and big data sectors, taking into account the exogenous factors as discussed through the PESTLE analysis. The research started taking into account the main 5GMETA offering both as technological features and value created, and also the forecasting of such trend and identifying the segment that could be penetrated from the 5GMETA platform. In addition, an overview of the direct and indirect competitors has been shown, analysing their business models and the technologies involved.

In this deliverable release, the stakeholder analysis has been performed based on a theoretical approach that includes possible interests, power and conflicts of identified stakeholders. The set of stakeholders includes both the general ones and the stakeholders more related to the use cases. The power/interest matrix highlights the stakeholder's segments and how the 5GMETA project should consider them, allowing us to understand those who have to be satisfied or just informed, those who have to be managed closely or those that could be neglected.

Both market and stakeholder analysis will be subject to further in-depth analysis, distributing a questionnaire to the possible stakeholders to compare and/or confute the hypothesis in this release.

This first release will be the foundation not only for the T6.1 (and its second and final deliverable) but also for other tasks and deliverables. Below we sketch the next steps that will be followed to evolve this version into the final one.

- M19: 1st Hackathon: Business oriented Hackaton. Requirements that will emerge will be reflected in D6.2
- M22: D6.2 “New business models – First version” Identification of innovative business models that can arise when the automotive ecosystem in Europe has a marketplace or a platform like 5GMETA.
- M25: Mid-term review
- M33: 2nd Hackathon: Wider business logic, models, and extraction of new technological requirements from the use cases envisioned and implemented in First Hackathons by SMEs and start-ups. Hackathon results will be embedded in D6.8 and D6.9. The requirements that will emerge from the interactions with the SMEs and companies during the hackathons will be reflected in the 5GMETA platform.
- M36: D6.8 “Market research and stakeholder mapping – Final version”. Sound strategy definition in terms of market opportunities, penetration, and development. Stakeholders’ identification and mapping.
- M38: D6.9 “New business models – Final version” Business model validation based on market analysis results and Hackaton outputs.
- M41: D6.6 “Market outreach plan” and D6.7 “Recommendations for fostering a new CCAM market ecosystem beyond 5GMETA” The market outreach plan will target the new markets identified in D6.8, with the objective of defining a strategy for commercialisation for the new market actors emerged in hackathons and incubators and considering the innovative business models described in D6.9.

Recommendations for business incubators, public authorities and other stakeholders to continue fostering new CCAM markets and actors.

Figure 13 5GMETA new market ecosystem roadmap

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⁵¹ Only the costs of the supervision work by LINKS have been reported and claimed within 5GMETA.